

Critical Framework for RELISH

sahar tavakoli, Andrea Borghini, 30 April 2026, Version No. 1.0

D4.1 Overview

PROJECT	RELISH
PROJECT NO.	101177427
WORKPACKAGE	WP4: PREPPING – Wrangling and Curating of Data
DELIVERABLE	D4.1
VERSION NO.	1.0
DUE DATE	April 30, 2026
SUBMISSION DATE	April 30, 2026
TYPE	Public
AUTHOR(S)	sahar tavakoli; Andrea Borghini
REVIEWER(S)	Liselotte Hedegaard; Jeffrey Newman; Mario Guilló; Janita Van Dyk; H. Rosi Song
APPROVER	H. Rosi Song

Document history

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR(S)	CHANGES
0.1	08/09/2025	sahar tavakoli, Andrea Borghini	Document creation
0.2	[31/01/2026]	sahar tavakoli, Andrea Borghini	Document expansion following initial feedback round
0.3	23/11/2025; 1/12/2025; 04/03/2026	Liselotte Hedegaard; Jeffrey Newman; Janita Van Dyk; H. Rosi Song;	Preliminary review and comments
0.4	15/04/2026	sahar tavakoli, Andrea Borghini	Document review based on comments
0.5	27/04/2026	Mario Guilló	Internal Review
0.6	29/04/2026	sahar tavakoli; Andrea Borghini	Final revisions
0.7	30/04/2026	H. Rosi Song	Coordinator Approved
1.0	30/04/2026	H. Rosi Song	Final Submission

Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
CA	Consortium Agreement	PC	Project Coordinator
cICH	Culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage	T[#]	Task No.
D[#]	Deliverable No.	TRIPS	Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights Agreement
EC	European Commission	UCD	User-Centred Design
GA	Grant Agreement	WP4	Work Package No. 4
ICH	Intangible Cultural Heritage		

Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alcía	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
Partner	University of Alicante	UA	Spain
Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo	UNISG	Italy
Partner	University of Milan	UMIL	Italy
Partner	University of Toronto	UoT	Canada

Legal disclaimer

RELISH is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101177427. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contents

D4.1 Overview	i
Document history	i
Abbreviations and acronyms	ii
Consortium	ii
Legal disclaimer	iii
Contents	iv
List of Tables	iv
List of Figures	v
Executive Summary	v
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Description of the document	1
1.1.1 <i>WPs and tasks related to the deliverable</i>	2
2 Rationale	2
2.1 On transdisciplinary collaboration and its challenges	3
3 Background and State of the Art	4
4 Philosophical and Critical Approach	8
5 Framework Map	9
6 Consortium Consultations	11
6.1 Interview design	12
6.2 Initial themes and reflections	13
6.3 Limits and delimitations	19
7 RELISH Glossary	20
8 Impact and Next Steps	24
9 Conclusions	25
10 Bibliography	27
Annex I: Transcripts	29
Interviewee 01	29
Interviewee 02	34
Interviewee 03	44
Interviewee 04	56
Interviewee 05	70
Interviewee 06	73

List of Tables

Table 1: D4.1 activities and rationale at-a-glance.	3
Table 2: RELISH glossary Relevant to cICH	20

List of Figures

Figure 1: A Map to Navigating cICH

10

Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.1: Critical Framework for RELISH was produced within WP4 PREPPING – Wrangling and Curating of Data, coordinated by the University of Milan.

The deliverable provides a preliminary framework for the consortium’s engagement with **culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage (cICH)**, including background context, methodological orientation, glossary of key terms, and a provisional key to guide future translations of RELISH findings into digital platforms. Its purpose is to establish a shared conceptual basis for consortium collaboration, while remaining flexible and adaptable to evolving disciplinary and community perspectives.

The document was completed by the **University of Milan (UMIL)**, with input and review from consortium partners in WP4, in cooperation with related activities in WP7 and WP8.

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of the EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

This deliverable was completed by the University of Milan (UMIL) as part of WP4 PREPPING – Wrangling and Curating of Data, in partial fulfilment of D4.1 – Critical Framework for RELISH. Its objectives are:

- To establish the theoretical and practical framework from which RELISH operates when dealing with existing research and information related to culinary cultural heritage.
- To support the User-Centred Design (UCD) approach of the technical partners in the consortium from a cultural heritage perspective by identifying key questions and cultural assumptions that are relevant for RELISH
- To assist partners in the development of key terms for analysis in culinary cultural activities organised on behalf of RELISH
- To identify and engage in conversation with institutional stakeholders in promoting culinary cultural heritage in local, national, and at EU level.

1.1 Description of the document

D4.1 establishes **the conceptual and methodological foundation** for the RELISH project's engagement with culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage (cICH). Produced within WP4, and coordinated by the University of Milan, the document introduces a preliminary, flexible framework and glossary to guide consortium partners in their approaches to culinary heritage.

1.1.1 WPs and tasks related to the deliverable

Coordinated, drafted, and completed by UMIL, WP4 T4.1 was developed with review and input from consortium partners at UDUR, ATU, BSC, CITY, FA, LYFE, IST, RUC, UCC, UA, and UNISG. T4.1 provides the theoretical and methodological foundations of RELISH, identifying cultural assumptions and questions relevant to ICH, and supporting technical partners by curating concepts and criteria that inform the design of the data-driven RELISH platform ahead of digitisation.

The framework offered here is further intended to guide and inform WP6 (TASTING – Piloting and Trials), WP7 (SIMMERING – Development and Testing), and WP8 (COOLING DOWN – Testing and Production), ensuring conceptual and methodological alignment across the consortium.

2 Rationale

Rather than offering a fixed schema, the RELISH critical framework offers a starting point for dialogue and collaboration across diverse disciplinary, professional, and community perspectives.

The deliverable is organised into four main sections:

1. **Background and State of the Art:** A short review of UNESCO's 2003 Convention on Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH), scholarly analysis of culinary heritage, and key tensions between intangible practices and traditional systems of tangible heritage documentation and preservation.
2. **Framework Map:** A provisional interpretive tool intended to bridge theoretical insights with the practical demands of developing the RELISH digital platform and related AI-driven applications.
3. **Consortium Consultations:** Current definitions, themes, and challenge areas defined by individual consortium leads, generated from semi-structured interviews with consortium leads.
4. **RELISH Glossary:** A set of central concepts (*e.g.*, recipe, authority, culture, community, tacit knowledge, territorialisation, standardisation) and definitions supporting cross-consortium communication and establishing a shared vocabulary.

Table 1: D4.1 activities and rationale at-a-glance.

ACTIVITY	RATIONALE	OUTPUT
Conduct literature Review	Identify definitions, tensions, and emerging tools	Brief synthesis
Design framework map	Create a shared pathway for navigating tensions and approaches regarding cICH	Figure (see Figure 1)
Generate user-centred perspectives	Semi-structured interviews to identify preliminary themes	Transcripts (see Annex I)
Collate a glossary of key terms	Outline key terms and concepts for the consortium	Short table (see Table 1)

The purpose of D4.1 is to centralise the theoretical and cultural heritage dimensions for RELISH and enable subsequent Work Packages (particularly WP6, WP7, and WP8) to build on a common conceptual foundation. It supports RELISH’s objectives by:

- Establishing the theoretical framework from which the consortium operates
- Identifying assumptions and questions relevant to the promotion of EU food culture
- Assisting partners in developing terms and criteria for analysis
- Preparing the ground for stakeholder engagement

As such, the Critical Framework provides consortium members with a core definitional document that is open to revision as RELISH progresses, adaptable to multiple disciplinary perspectives, and oriented toward supporting collaboration between philosophers, social scientists, heritage practitioners, technologists, and institutional actors.

2.1 On transdisciplinary collaboration and its challenges

A stated aim of the Horizon Europe programme is to foster transdisciplinary collaboration (European Commission Directorate General for Communication 2024). In keeping with this larger programme, D4.1 is designed to operate across disciplinary, professional, and community boundaries. This transdisciplinary approach goes beyond multidisciplinary collaboration, as it does not simply place perspectives side by side but instead seeks to integrate them into shared ways of working.

In the context of cICH, this means combining insights from cultural heritage studies, gastronomy, digital humanities, philosophy, science and technology studies, computer science, law, and community practice.

Transdisciplinary work offers significant opportunities—it enables the consortium to address complex issues, such as how to:

- **Safeguard** culinary practices without fixing them into static forms
- **Integrate** sustainability concerns into heritage documentation
- **Apply** digital tools to embodied and tacit knowledge.

At the same time, this mode of collaboration raises challenges. It requires partners to adapt their disciplinary assumptions, to adjust professional vocabularies, and to negotiate different expectations about what counts as evidence or authority.

For these reasons, the framework presented in this deliverable is introduced as **preliminary and adaptable**. Its purpose is to establish a starting point for dialogue across RELISH. By keeping the framework open and flexible, the consortium can accommodate multiple perspectives, support collaboration across diverse fields, and allow the framework to evolve as the project develops.

3 Background and State of the Art

This section outlines a brief discussion on current definitions, challenges, and new strategies related to Culinary Heritage (both tangible and intangible forms) from policy and scholarly perspectives. We derived the following implications for culinary heritage after a review of existing literature and policy documents, and discuss them further below:

1. Culinary heritage is both material and immaterial, transmitted and dynamic—it can elide many extant tools and frameworks for material heritage recognition and valorisation;
2. Traditional and evolving policy and digital approaches to recognising cICH can struggle with the context-dependent and evolving nature of culinary cultural transmission;
3. Digital tools can offer new directions for recognising cICH, but are not without opportunities for reconsideration and adaptation.

Articulated in response to limitations within traditional registers of heritage preservation, the UNESCO “Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage” has, since its adoption in 2003, served as a referent for subsequent projects aimed at identifying, conserving, and/or promoting embodied or otherwise

intangible cultural practices at international, national, community, and individual scales (Aikawa 2004). Defined in Article 2 of the 2003 Convention, ICH encompasses

“[P]ractices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills—as well as instruments, objects, artefacts, and cultural spaces associated therewith—that communities, groups, and, in some cases, individuals recognise as part of their cultural heritage.” (UNESCO 2003)

The 2010 inclusion of the French Gastronomic Meal, the Mediterranean diet, and the traditional Mexican cuisine of Michoacán into UNESCO’s Representative List marked **the first recognition of culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage** (hereafter, cICH) as a distinct focus within ICH, highlighting particular connections to identity, community, and the performance or practice of everyday life.

cICH’s recent inclusion draws attention to the **many difficulties in recognising food-related forms of cultural practices and materials as forms of *intangible* cultural heritage**. Traditional regimes of order (databases, archives, museums, registers, and catalogues, for example) historically grounded their authority in what is evident, measurable, and materially verifiable (Foucault 1989). The intangible world stands in direct contrast to such logics: eluding materiality, resisting measurement, maintaining fluidity and context-dependency.

This definitional indefiniteness creates a persistent tension between intangible subjects and established systems of documentation, representation, and preservation. The uneasy relationship between intangible subjects and ordering systems are evident in current scholarship on cICH in the form of three, overlapping concerns:

1. **The challenge of documentation:** how to record practices that are inherently intangible, ephemeral, and relational (Partarakis et al. 2021).
2. **The question of representation:** how to make visible and legible that which is ineffable without reducing practices to static forms or objects (Springstubb, 2018).
3. **The issue of dynamism:** how to safeguard traditions while acknowledging ongoing (and, at times, disjunctive) change, innovation, migration, and evolving social values (Appadurai 1996; Bortolotto 2007; Brulotte and Giovine 2016).

Together, these concerns highlight the need for methods and tools that work with forms of culinary heritage’s intangibility and context-dependency.

Innovations in digital heritage and museology have begun to respond to tensions—both existing and arising—in processes of documenting ICH. Across museology,

anthropology, and heritage studies, digitisation is put forward as both opportunity and challenge, or, indeed, as a challenge inspiring new directions (Kenderdine et al. 2021). Giaccardi (2006), for example, emphasises how digital heritage approaches operate through both duplication and extension; enabling recombination, personalisation, and interconnection even as they unsettle assumptions about originality and fixity. To such a point, Hou et al. (2022) have elaborated on the inadequacy of any single digital representation to fully capture a subject as plural in the form of cultural heritage. Experts emphasise the need for plural manifestations, as well as establishing shared ontologies that support operation across collections and communities (Hou et al. 2022).

Kenderdine et al. (2007), meanwhile, take a somewhat different approach, arguing instead that scholars and practitioners approach digital media as way to reconsider and change how forms of heritage are recognised, documented, or valued as “objects.” That is, these scholars ask stakeholders to consider not only how we might go about transforming modes of access and participation, but how analyst understandings of objecthood and presence co-produce that which is documented.

For example, projects using audiovisual archives, digital storytelling, immersive environments, and participatory platforms have proliferated (Udeaja et al. 2021; Wilson and Desha 2016), with aims to broaden public access, create durable resources for research and education, and to provide communities with tools that facilitate the transmission of knowledge.

These digital approaches offer **key considerations and opportunities for cICH**, and ICH in general. Much of this work remains **object-centred**: databases and repositories continue to prioritise textual or visual documentation over the embodied, performative, and relational aspects of ICH, reducing such acts of transfer to discrete, fixed representations and reproducing epistemologies suited to tangible heritage (Kirshenblatt-Gimblett 2014; Taylor 2003). Just as traditional museums and archives value objects that are measurable, visible, and stable, these **digital projects can treat ICH as if it were an object**: something to be recorded, stored, and classified.

More generally, **culinary traditions exemplify the broader contradictions of ICH**. Culinary traditions rely on memory and repetition, but emerge out of adaptation, improvisation, and context-specific knowledge (Holtzman 2006; Lee 2023; Sutton 2008). Recipes function as **performative utterances**: their significance emerges in the moment of action, yet preservation efforts often emphasise replicable outputs rather than processes (Borghini 2015; Giovannucci et. al. 2010). Codifications can simplify intentionally vague instructions—such as “to taste” or “as needed”—translating relational, sensory, and experiential knowledge into fixed, textual forms.

At the intersection of cultural heritage and intellectual property (IP) law, the Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights Agreement (TRIPS) and its system of Geographical Indications further complicate matters. In these frameworks, food heritage is governed not only as cultural property but also as an economic and legal resource. While such mechanisms aim to safeguard practices and establish market value, they can also produce exclusions by restricting who is authorised to produce, represent, or benefit from recognised forms of heritage, effectively contributing to the monopolisation of cultural practices (Echols 2016; Giovannucci et al. 2010).

These tensions underscore the need for frameworks that attend simultaneously to tradition, innovation, and the material, legal, and social infrastructures that shape culinary heritage.

Rather than presenting a fixed schema, the framework below serves as a practical guide for exploring how different disciplinary, community, and digital perspectives interact in the study of cICH. It is intended to support dialogue, adaptation, and collaborative problem-solving, while taking into account the changing and evolving nature of the practices themselves. The framework does not resolve the challenges involved in documenting, representing, or preserving culinary heritage; instead, it offers a way to engage with these issues and to consider how knowledge, culture, and law intersect in the kitchen and beyond.

Key Considerations:

cICH involves:

- Cultural norms: traditions, shared meanings, identities
- Social dynamics: transmission, adaptation, innovation
- Academic perspectives: analysis, critique, and systematisation
- Infrastructures: legislation, policy, archives, materials, regulation, digitisation
- Authority and expertise: scientific, technical, bureaucratic actors, certifications, public recognition
- Established conventions and assumptions: Preservation, conservation, documentation
- Philosophical and empirical tensions: objectivity, stasis, recognition, difference

4 Philosophical and Critical Approach

In designing a critical framework, UMIL borrowed from the analytic orientation of Science and Technology Studies (STS), a field that focusses on the production of knowledge, technology, and the effects of scientific and technical expertise on wider publics (and vice versa).

A key framework from STS increasingly used outside of the field (*e.g.*, project management; research collaboration; Knowledge Translation and Transfer [KTT]) relates to “boundary work” and “boundary objects”:

Boundary work: How people and institutions use knowledge and language to create “boundaries” between cultural spaces and fields (*e.g.*, “science” and “scientists” vs. “publics” and “non-experts”), as well as attribute differing qualities between these spaces and actors to demarcate these boundaries (Thomas Gieryn 1999).

Boundary object: An object, which intersects multiple cultural spaces, and which is defined differently by different actors within those spaces. Examples include, *e.g.*, repositories, records, specimens, and methods. A boundary object satisfies differing needs, values, and criteria across spaces and has a common identity, despite definitional variation (Star and Griesemer 1989).

RELISH is a consortium involving multiple forms of scientific, expert, and technical stakeholders responsible to various communities and publics in its approaches, design, and output. Thus, STS provides a helpful orientation to identifying boundary work and boundary objects related to and encompassing **culinary heritage and recipes**.

Using the term **boundary work**, this critical framework considers that cultural spaces and objects are not necessarily pre-given but are produced within and out of interactions and investments. In other words, recognising and researching cICH is a process of differentiation, not reconciling differences.

Using the term **boundary object** (referenced previously in RELISH D10.2), culinary heritage or cICH and recipes can have shared identities across spaces and connect stakeholders, but precisely because they can hold different, and often incommensurable, meanings, methods, and priorities.

5 Framework Map

The framework map is introduced as a practical interpretive tool for navigating the tensions identified throughout this report. In particular, it responds to the difficulty of reconciling Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) with conventional heritage approaches, which tend to prioritise stable, documentable, and material forms. Generated from this core tension, the map does not seek to resolve differences or impose a single framework. Instead, it offers a way of situating and working across diverse perspectives, helping consortium members to recognise how varying assumptions, priorities, and forms of expertise intersect when approaching heritage and recipes. In this sense, the map is intended to support reflection, dialogue, and collaboration, rather than closure.

A Map to Navigating cICH

Figure 1: A Map to Navigating cICH

6 Consortium Consultations

RELISH's approach to cICH considers the cultural dynamism, multiple meanings, and regulatory needs to approach forms of ICH.

A key consideration in this report is that **heritage** (as well as culinary heritage) **has no one single and fixed definition**. Instead, stakeholders value, define, and engage with heritage from multiple disciplinary conventions and assumptions.

This does not mean that efforts to engage and recognise forms of culinary heritage is a failed endeavour. Instead, robust frameworks and methods can use difference and negotiation to enrich tools, methods, and frameworks in cultural heritage projects from grounded and multi-disciplinary collaboration.

To identify the variety of consortium perspectives on cICH, UMIL consulted with consortium members by conducting interviews with WP Leads, who have differing expertise in humanities, social sciences, and culinary fields, in June and July 2025. Transcripts from these interviews are appended to this report (see Annex I).

Interviews were semi-structured, generating responses to open-ended questions on how culinary heritage becomes an object of inquiry and practice in order to identify:

- Methodological preferences, sensitivities, priorities, and critiques
- Differences in orientation, such as compatibilities, situated knowledge, incommensurability of perspectives, disagreements

Generating these responses assists RELISH in demonstrating the variety of preferences and orientations within the consortium that inform the frameworks and key terms later introduced in the report.

As noted above, we highlight that disagreements and divergences are not obstacles to resolve. They are instead necessary elements of collaborative practices that allow for pluralistic and open-ended interpretation and output.

Relatedly, complementarity or consensus in definitions, approaches, or orientations can also create challenges; as discussed in the previous sections, unchanging practices and frameworks can be slow to adapt or ill-fitted to guide frameworks for intangible practices and cultural forms.

6.1 Interview design

Three open-ended guiding questions were used to frame discussion:

1. From your disciplinary or professional perspective, what considerations or sensitivities should guide the way we approach or discuss Intangible Cultural Heritage and recipes?
2. What elements would you most like to see included in a methodological framework for engaging with Intangible Cultural Heritage and recipes?
3. Are there any approaches, assumptions, or tendencies you would prefer to see avoided when studying or working with Intangible Cultural Heritage and recipes?

Interviewers adapted the guiding questions above for different interviewees to better elicit responses. They also supplemented them with additional follow-up queries.

The questions were designed to encourage reflection rather than prescriptive responses. The flexible approach taken ensured that the interviews captured a wide range of viewpoints, providing material that was both comparative across disciplines and sensitive to the nuances of individual perspectives. Moreover, it allowed for methodological disagreement, hesitation, and critique to surface without forcing premature resolution.

Interviewees were invited to shape the conversation according to their expertise and interests, ensuring that perspectives emerged organically. Interviews frequently extended beyond the above-listed guiding questions, incorporating examples from interviewees' own work, reflections from prior collaborations, and anticipations regarding future project activities.

Early in the process, the wording of questions was adjusted to reflect a common tendency among participants to use “recipe” and “culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage” interchangeably. The revised phrasing (“Intangible Cultural Heritage *and* recipes”) was adopted both to recognise this usage and to clarify the distinction between the two concepts. This adjustment is itself informative of the conceptual overlap and slippage within the broader network of the consortium.

Drawing on the approach to **boundary work** (outlined in Section 3), interviewees' terminological choices and methodological preferences become forms of data in and of themselves: they express how epistemic boundaries are drawn, negotiated, disseminated, and brought to closure in collaborative settings (Gieryn 1983; Knorr Cetina 1999; Pinch 1996). That is, rather than resolving difference, our analysis here aims to render difference visible within a shared collaborative space.

All the original transcripts were anonymised and digitally secured. After interviews were completed with the 6 interviewees, we identified several notable preliminary themes and brief reflections for partners that best illustrate areas of shared or differing interpretation. Selected quotes were lightly edited or condensed for clarity.

6.2 Initial themes and reflections

There are many ways of interpreting the interview responses, and we invite readers to explore the transcripts in full. We selected some relevant examples below to initiate reflection.

On *recipes*, some interviewees were hesitant regarding the purpose of creating a **shared or basic definition**:

Interviewee 1 “We probably have to assume ... that we have an understanding, an ontology of recipes, but I’m not sure if that’s true ... Or, should we approach our own case studies and individual research with a more comprehensive and insightful understanding of the theory, not only the method, to produce something that is innovative and ‘cutting edge?’”

Interviewee 4 “If we go into the project and be like the person who walks into a forest with a preconceived idea of a particular kind of plant and throws out everything else and then walks out of the forest and says, ‘Well, there are no plants there’ ... I don’t know whether we should be agreeing to a completely capacious definition of a recipe.”

Interviewees discussed thinking about writing recipes as ways to **resist standardisation**, as a **process**, or as a **“mode” of codification**:

Interviewee 4 “I’m trying to think of recipes as environmental acts.”
“We should be thinking about writing recipes that resists standardisation, that is willing for you to go produce something and for me to go produce something that is totally different and we’re okay with that.”

Interviewee 6 “So for me, the question of, *can sugar be a recipe*, that is equivalent in ‘recipe-ness’ to something like the 65 ingredient recipes of Ottolenghi or something—I would answer yes, it can, in that they’re both being turned into this codified form that is itself ‘the recipe.’ As soon as that mode is being employed, it’s a recipe to me.”

Interviewee 5

“In a way, it is ‘nothing’: a recipe does not mean taste, or show you how to eat it, or who you should eat it with. It is just a record that maybe does not record anything real. Or it is a reminder. And then you make the recipe, but you don’t actually make the recipe because that’s not how you cook. You always have to change because your kitchen is different, the season is different, the time is different, your age is different, you can’t get this ingredient, you don’t eat it in the right company. So already there are contradictions. Of course, writing down a recipe is not wrong, sometimes it is good, sometimes even political, but we should not pretend it’s really this ‘thing’ in the world.”

Recipes as **historically** and **culturally dependent** in both meaning and form also frequently came up in interviews, but in differing ways, highlighting techniques, exclusions, and power relations, and individual subjectivity:

Interviewee 1

“I don’t want to criticise anybody ... because it’s not their field, it’s not what they usually do; maybe they do have one hundred percent ‘comprehension’ of the multi-form, multifarious ways of culinary, gastronomic knowledge that recipes provide. But maybe they operate ... because it might be easier or productive for them ... starting from, I would say, more a nineteenth-century Anglo-Protestant concept of what a recipe is. I’m going to call it ‘traditional,’ but a traditional and super Western idea of what the recipe is. That excludes, for example, orality, or any recipes that can be found in popular culture or personal documents, from letters to autobiographies to handwritten domestic cookbooks, and so on and so forth.”

Interviewee 2

“Recipes *illuminate* the world they come from, right? So that illumination can be sort of the historical in the present, but it could be also in the past.”

“I think that in terms of cooking and dishes and ingredients and recipes ... it’s a lot more fleeting and it’s a lot more complicated. Because subjectivity and culture that you bring into the act of eating and taste—your own experience of eating food and what you enjoy, what you don’t—is so subjective.”

Interviewee 4

“Cookbooks are the act of collecting recipes and recipes depend on the time period. And they depend on what has been done. Have they gone through the process of printing? Have they gone through the process of editing? Have they gone through the process of ... intentionality? Fundamentally for me—and where I chafe a bit at the sort of rush to collect, collect, collect—is that a recipe that’s been written on the back of a note card and shoved into a kitchen drawer is a different phenomenon to some other particular kind of collecting. There’s a

different action there. A recipe from 1700 is very different to a recipe from 1900. In some sense, you might think of a recipe as a kind of ‘modern act’—as an act of modernism. What that involves is an effort at reproducibility.”

“Maybe what I’m arguing for is to accept and push forward with a definition of the recipe ... that sees a specific thing with specific kinds of power relations built in.”

Similar to discussions of *recipes*, **hesitancy to define forms of cultural heritage or heritage in general** also emerged, due to the subjectivity, variability, or dynamism interviewees attributed:

Interviewee 2 “Heritage is not so much the product, but the doing.”

“Even if intangible culture has a representation, they’re so varied at the end of the day—it can change. It’s not fixed.”

Interviewee 3 “Within a context, there are a lot of implicit meanings, assumptions. They really provide the specificities of their cultural context, which we also call *heritage*. So, the very same behaviour, the very same tools, in one context to another have, of course, completely different meanings. So, we are thinking of *heritages*.”

“It is like we are condemned as humans to chase things that are ideal or impossible, right? Nobody can define, I don’t know, *love* or *beauty*. But it doesn’t mean you don’t try to find it. You can define. I think the same here [with forms of heritage]. We have to say where they are, to point at them somehow.”

Interviewees spoke on the **economic and political dimensions of heritage**, particularly as an institution or as a system, in general or from their respective areas and fields:

Interviewee 1: “Basically ... the heritagisation of Italian and Italian cuisine [is] for the ultimate purpose of patenting what Italian food, Italian cuisine, really are, and valorise it in the world...with the extra label of ‘world human heritage.’ I think the ultimate goal is to make these [foods] valuable both in terms of the economy of Italy—I mean, the export of food and wine is an unbelievably important item in Italian international trade and economy—but also in political terms, that it is important these connections keep going through generations, are valorised for diplomatic uses, for the sense of belonging to an Italian nation, which is more global than ever.”

Interviewees likewise drew attention to **how they placed increased attention or usage of “food heritage” terminology in a specific historical moment** or set of concerns (particularly the Covid-19 pandemic):

Interviewee 3 “[In Italy during the pandemic] it wasn’t just a matter of heritage, it was more a matter of politics, in a broad sense. There were stakes. It is about social engagement, participation, education...”

Interviewee 6 “There was this period during the pandemic where I was binge listening to a lot of podcasts, and something I was listening to was the BBC Food Program, and after a period of time, I noticed they really started to lean in on this idea of tradition and foods tied to particular people, and those people being tied to geographies, and the whole thing being under threat ... This really got me started on thinking of how we are using the ways in which we talk about food to actually talk about people ... that’s how I got really interested in food as a population management or production system.”

Interviewees also reflected on the **differences between tangible and intangible cultural heritage**, and the tensions or problems involved:

Interviewee 2 “I think that even though [institutions] use the word ‘intangible,’ there is this tension in which in order to make something intangible valuable, you have to make it tangible. Perhaps what intangibility should highlight is the negotiation that has to go into making something tangible.”

Interviewee 3 “[Intangibility] is sort of implicit, it has to deal with knowledge, that which is tacit. But it’s not even that. There are implicit aspects, codes within a community of norms.”

Intangible culture as an *information system*—“you have to enter into a system, give some positive entries, fingerprints in some other places, or you have the tools or behaviours ... But can any of those then define the ‘intangible’? I think no. So, there is a part of the gap, that it’s not the game of heritage to study traces; perhaps those traces are not heritage at all ... You think you are doing something because you are reusing the tools [in the information system]—you can have reenactment, you can have mocking, you can have whatever ... but there is so much more to knowing. We’re moving in the gap, rather than in the traces.”

Interviewee 5 “When I think of intangibility, the first thing for me is that it’s not really intangible, no? We want intangibility and then we show tangible things, we take measures, we make pictures, we want to put it in a database, to make a platform. So, I get a big suspicious when we talk about the intangible as something that just floats, as if we can catch it and then put

it somewhere more safe, because usually, or really, what is called intangible is precisely what *can't* be put in a database.”

Interviewee 6 “The idea that you would have a registry of intangibility makes no sense, because intangibility is not registerable. It’s almost like a codification of tacit knowledge—that makes no sense.”

Many interviewees raised strong critiques and limitations of institutionalised heritage definitions and frameworks:

Interviewee 3 “It’s a danger for me that I see in a lot of the UNESCO Heritage Lists—it has that potential defect that it seems like, ‘This is the culture,’ and then *boom*, it’s codified. Then everybody, communities, individuals, they don’t really recognise themselves in that. They see that as an institutional representation, almost imposition, of what cultures are, and it’s not alive, you know? It misses all the lively parts of culture ... It has the same problem as Geographic Indications. Everybody knows that they’re using them for commercial purposes. It’s a product, managed by producers. Yes, there is an international frame, a governmental frame, but in the end, you are talking about products that are sold. But if you are trying to represent intangible cultural heritage, it’s not immediately a product that is sold, or if that’s what you’re trying to do, then that shouldn’t be the case.”

Interviewee 5 “When I think of heritage in these EU languages, like ‘safeguarding,’ I’m like, *okay*, but from what? What change? From mixing? From people moving? Because change is not always loss. Sometimes it’s survival.”

“It doesn’t celebrate *Oh, look how we change, how we evolve, have evolved*; it’s always more like, *We are so fragile, we could be lost any time*, and all this ‘hybridity’ becomes corruption. And then when recipes enter this picture, they can easily become ways of hiding these bad things. We preserve a place’s recipes, and we don’t say that they made this recipe because they stole it from some other place in the world, or that these ingredients come from a land they invaded. I think it is a big problem RELISH has.”

“Another problem is this thing about being *old*. Heritage is always old, like it’s eighteenth century ... but why? And this is not always true. We are always reinventing. It is adaptation. That doesn’t make these recipes less meaningful.”

Interviewee 6 “Within the sphere of heritage studies—within critiques of heritage work—there has been a lot of discussion about how this sort of preservation has a troublesome Western ... let’s just say *flavour* to it. I

see recipes doing the same thing. If the Western mode is this record keeping, archiving mode, like ... the emergence of 'Western civilisation' here, then this sort of drive to make the archive, to make the recipe, to record it, to recognise it as a specific form rather than a continuation of other practice. There might be a context in which, for example, a recipe might be considered part of a song, or mnemonic, or something like that in another context, right? But to pull it out and say that this can be 'recipified' ... it is this reassertion of a form of ordering that I guess is doing this exclusion work, this border-making work."

One also forwarded **an alternative framework for intangible cultural heritage** stemming from a recent RELISH activity:

Interviewee 2 "Heritage ... gives you a framework, I guess, a sort of a boundary. The more you think about it, the less of a kind of guiding principle of critical insight it is. It's not a critical lens anymore. Perhaps it's more of a tool. It will be an instrument. Not so much about understanding the past, but to take an assessment of your present, what kind of negotiations you have to enter, to find value in a common practice that you want to take forward..."

"I feel like heritage is no longer or shouldn't be past facing, but rather future facing ... I think that whatever you're preserving, or whatever existed in the past, eventually loses value. I mean, you have to make value, you have to find meaning to make it valuable, and that production of value is cultural negotiation. Then all the competing interests, all the institutions: Where is it top down? Where is it bottoms up? Who gets involved? Who are the stakeholders? All of those things are coming into play as well."

Finally, interviewees commented on the challenges, limitations, and implications of project collaboration, or to the RELISH project as a whole:

Interviewee 2 "There's a very diplomatic dance going on ... so when you arrive at a consensus, there are a lot of things being lost. In the process of making intangible into tangible, it should be as inclusive as it can be, and we should also recognise our limitations."

Interviewee 4 "This project isn't just talking about European food legacies, it's also remaking, reasserting Europe. It's defining Europe in the process of making legacies in Europe."

"I don't have an image in mind of what I want this project to look like, but I certainly have a lot of ideas in my head of what I *don't* want it to look like and what I'm afraid it will look like."

“But there’s maybe something to being content with the limits. We should have words that are just, ‘Sorry, you can’t translate this,’ ‘This is too located,’ ‘This is not a mobile ingredient,’ or the recipe you should not make because you’re not entitled to it. I think we need to be really careful with this big data set.”

Interviewee 6

On a database for European gastronomic legacy—“The thing that is missing for me is the *why?* And the *against what?* This attempt to form a database of European gastronomic legacy, *Why?* Who’s threatening the legacy of Europe? Where was Europe not recorded? It’s not clear to me why it’s needed. As soon as it becomes a matter of European gastronomic legacies, it’s implying that what is being reclaimed or recaptured is out of some muck of not-European gastronomic legacies. Especially in a continent whose foodstuffs have been so shaped by its historic legacy of going to everywhere else in the world and naming everywhere else in the world, defining the rest of the world, and so on. So, I guess I’ve been stuck for a year and a bit on why this is needed.”

Based on the themes here and the full appended transcripts, we consider areas of alignment and disagreement as valuable. Alignments indicate where a shared framework can be readily established, while divergences highlight where negotiation or flexibility will be required.

Disagreements took multiple forms, including explicitly articulated methodological incompatibility (for example, differing members’ commitments to quantitative versus qualitative approaches, or divergent assumptions about the conceptual stability of objects such as “recipes” or “heritage,” understood as either fixed or dynamic), as well as personalised or indirect expressions of critique, referencing the practices, assumptions, relevance, or presumed knowledgeability of other consortium members.

We treat these discussions and divergences as analytically significant, offering insight into how boundaries are drawn and contested in practice.

Taken together, these interviews informed the development of a RELISH glossary, and function as practical tools for engaging with heritage and recipes across diverse and sometimes incommensurable perspectives.

6.3 Limits and delimitations

The findings presented in this deliverable reflect input from consortium leads during a defined and limited period (June–July 2025). As such, they represent a snapshot of

perspectives at an early stage of the project rather than a definitive account. Individual consortium members’ views should therefore be understood as situated, provisional, and shaped by the specific moment of project formation. Variation in documentation methods (transcription versus *post hoc* notes) also means that contributions differ in depth and level of detail.

The glossary and framework developed in the next section should therefore be understood as provisional tools. They are designed to capture a figurative “line of best fit” across diverse disciplinary, professional, and community perspectives, while acknowledging that some differences cannot be fully reconciled. In particular, deeply held methodological commitments or epistemic priorities may remain incommensurable, requiring ongoing negotiation rather than synthesis.

Accordingly, both the glossary list and framework remain open to revision as the project evolves. They are intended to support communication and collaboration within the consortium, while allowing space for perspectives to shift and expand over the course of RELISH. Future iterations of this framework may incorporate additional voices, revised terminology, or alternative methodological emphases.

7 RELISH Glossary

The review of background literature and transcript discussions resulted in the development of a working glossary and a preliminary interpretive framework (Section 7). The glossary emerged as a response to observed terminological variation and conceptual ambiguity, rather than as a predefined output. It is intended that these resources serve as practical tools for consortium partners, supporting communication across disciplines and informing the design and implementation of later project activities.

Table 2: RELISH glossary Relevant to cICH

TERM	DESCRIPTION/DEFINITION	SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS
RECIPE	A performative utterance, whose meaning or identity is realised and fixed only in use. Recipes can act as boundary objects, supporting coordination across different disciplinary or community perspectives while remaining adaptable to context.	Bijker et al. 1989; Borghini 2015; Star and Griesemer 1989

TERM	DESCRIPTION/DEFINITION	SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS
AUTHORITY / EXPERT/ EXPERTISE	Forms of knowledge and recognition that are socially constructed and context dependent. Technical skill also validated through communal recognition (such as certification, apprenticeship). Authority emerges when particular actors or groups are granted the power to stabilise meanings, practices, or identities within a field, though these settlements remain open to contestation.	Bijker et al. 1989; Borghini 2015
CULTURE	Shared practices and 'webs of significance' (networks of symbols, meanings, beliefs) through which individuals interpret and organise life, identity, continuity, and creativity. Culture is lived, plural, open to contestation, and ongoing in development.	Geertz 1973; UNESCO 1972
HERITAGE	The transformation of cultural practices into objects of preservation, display, and value, or the physical/tangible legacy of intangible practice.	Kirshenblatt-Gimblett 2014; Muñoz 2006; UNESCO 1972
TRADITION	A practice or representation (genuinely longstanding or recently invented, reinterpreted, or adapted) presented as continuous with the past, constructed to establish authority, legitimacy, or identity.	Billig 1995; Hobsbawm et al. 1992
IDENTITY	Not fixed but performed and managed situationally, shaped by context, shared or directed recognition, and alignment with tradition. Though dynamic, identity is framed as a stable category in cultural policy.	Austin 1975; Goffman 2022
COMMUNITY	A collective defined by shared practices, traditions, or identifications. These can be relational as well as porous, constituted through shared belonging as well as by boundaries or exclusions. Like Authority/Experts, community recognises, maintains, or transmits intangible heritage.	Anderson 1991; Cohen 2015
TACIT / EMBODIED KNOWLEDGE	Forms of knowing that resist articulation into text or code or formal instruction: embodied in practice (situated experience), enacted through doing (gestures, senses), transmitted via apprenticeship rather than formal instruction.	Polanyi 2015

TERM	DESCRIPTION/DEFINITION	SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS
PRACTICE / ENACTMENT / TRANSFER	Modes and gestures of doing, embodying, or sharing/transferring social or cultural life.	Bourdieu 1977; Lave & Wenger 1991; Reckwitz 2002; Taylor 2003
TYPICALITY	Properties born of relational, rather than fixed, configurations between ingredient, technique, practice, symbolic meaning, and historical memory. Though at times mutually informative, typicality and authenticity are not and ought not be treated as synonymous terms.	Parasecoli 2022; <i>See also RELISH D4.2 – Madera Gómez & Borghini 2026</i>
AUTHENTICITY	An effect of material and symbolic practices through which singularity, provenance, and temporal continuity are mobilised to structure and, later, stabilise distinction, origin, and tradition around objects.	Benjamin 1968; Bourdieu 1984; Callon et al. 2002
DOCUMENTATION / PROOF / EVIDENCE	Processes and artefacts used to record, substantiate, or legitimise claims. What counts as evidence depends on conventions, institutions, and trust (<i>Refer to: AUTHORITY / EXPERTISE / EXPERTS</i>).	Gieryn 1999; Latour 1987; Shapin and Schaffer 2011
INTANGIBILITY	That which is living, embodied, and transmitted through people rather than objects. What counts as ‘intangible’ is defined by the techniques of documentation, preservation, and regulation that render practices both knowable and protectable. That is, the intangible can be made tangible by changing perspectives on what constitutes evidence.	Lampland and Star 2009; Muñoz 2006
TERRITORIALISATION/ PLACE	Processes/actions/symbols that tie practice, product, and/or identity to place—a process that adds meaning or value to space.	Deleuze & Guattari 1987; Casey 1996; Barham 2003
STANDARDISATION	The production of uniformity across practices, materials, or representations, often through codification, measurement, or similar such apparatuses of regulation (PDOs, labelling, data models, for example). Though standardisation enables comparability and legal recognition, it	Star and Griesemer 1989; Timmermans and Epstein 2010

TERM	DESCRIPTION/DEFINITION	SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS
	poses a challenge to the variation and local specificity of cICH.	
SUBSTITUTION	Processes through which ingredients, techniques, tools, or gestures are replaced or exchanged within a practice while maintaining recognisability or legitimacy. Substitution highlights how recipes and culinary practices persist through change, adaptation, constraint, or migration. Rather than signalling loss or degradation, substitution can function as a mode of continuity, evidencing the flexibility and situated judgement involved in practice.	Borghini 2015; Holtzman 2006; Sutton 2008; Timmermans and Epstein 2010
VARIABILITY	The capacity of a practice, recipe, or heritage form to accommodate difference across performances, contexts, and practitioners. Variability foregrounds plurality rather than deviation, challenging models of authenticity or standardisation that privilege uniform reproduction. In the context of cICH, variability is not noise to be eliminated but a constitutive feature of living traditions.	Bortolotto 2007; Kirshenblatt-Gimblett 2014; Reckwitz 2002; Taylor 2003
STABILITY / FIXITY	The temporary settling of meanings, practices, or categories such that they appear coherent, bounded, or repeatable. Stability is often treated as a prerequisite for documentation, comparison, or regulation, but is achieved through social, technical, and institutional work rather than given in advance.	Bijker et al. 1987; Latour 1987; Timmermans and Epstein 2010
FLEXIBILITY	The capacity of a framework, representation, or practice to remain open to adjustment, negotiation, and reinterpretation across contexts. Flexibility is frequently positioned in tension with authority, standardisation, and proof, yet is necessary for engaging with dynamic, embodied, and community-based forms of cICH.	Bijker et al. 1987; Lampland and Star 2009; Star and Griesemer 1989
INNOVATION	Point of difference and deferral for 'tradition' or 'continuity'. Not solely technological, innovation emerges in cultural and institutional contexts. Similarly, innovation is not definitional threatening to tradition and can be understood as necessary to continued practice in changing place.	Hobsbawm and Ranger 1992; Callon 1986; Godin 2015

8 Impact and Next Steps

The framework developed in D4.1 is intended primarily as a working resource for RELISH partners. It should be read not as a fixed model, but as a shared reference for navigating differences in how culinary heritage, recipes, and cICH are understood across the consortium. In particular, the glossary, interview materials, and framework map are designed to support communication between cultural, technical, and institutional partners, helping to make underlying assumptions and points of tension more explicit in collaborative work.

Looking ahead, the framework is expected to evolve alongside the project. Its terms, themes, and interpretive tools may be refined as RELISH progresses into later work packages, where conceptual considerations will need to be translated into practical and technical applications. Feedback from partners, as well as insights arising from pilot activities and platform development, will provide opportunities to revise and expand the framework where needed.

In terms of next steps, several areas of activity can be anticipated:

1. Use within RELISH to:

- Support communication between partners, especially across technical and cultural domains
- Inform the interpretation and structuring of data, case studies, and platform design
- Provide a shared vocabulary for discussing key concepts and tensions

2. Ongoing refinement:

- Iterative revision of the conceptual map and the glossary
- Potential expansion of themes based on findings of subsequent WPs

3. Internal dissemination (UMIL/WP4):

- Presentation of key findings and tools in consortium meetings or workshops
- Integration of the framework into guidance materials for project partners
- Use of the framework to support alignment across work packages

4. Broader implications for ICH/CH communities:

- Highlights ongoing tensions between dynamic cultural practices and systems of documentation, preservation, and regulation
- Suggests the value of flexible, plural frameworks for engaging with cICH
- Demonstrates how transdisciplinary collaboration can be structured around difference rather than consensus

5. Potential external engagement:

- Future dissemination through academic publications, conference presentations, or policy-oriented outputs
- Engagement with stakeholders such as heritage practitioners, policymakers, and community groups
- Exploration of how similar frameworks might be adapted for other cultural heritage or digital humanities projects

9 Conclusions

D4.1 has set out the conceptual, methodological, and practical foundations upon which RELISH will build its engagement with cICH. By combining background analysis, consortium member informed dialogues, a provisional framework map, and a glossary, what is offered here is a flexible structure intended to guide the consortium's collective work moving forward.

Emphasised within this deliverable is the importance of recognising that **cICH is not easily accommodated within traditional systems of documentation or preservation**. Culinary practices are dynamic, embodied, and context-dependent; they cannot be reduced without loss to static representations or codified outputs.

The framework presented thus does not aspire to finality and instead acknowledges the tensions between tradition and innovation, between safeguarding and change, and between academic abstraction and community practice. These tensions should not be regarded as obstacles but as productive spaces from which new forms of collaboration and understanding can emerge.

The glossary and interpretive tools developed are intentionally provisional. Their value lies less in closure than in their ability to mediate dialogue—between disciplines, between technical and cultural partners, and between institutional actors and community stakeholders. In this sense, the framework cultivates a transdisciplinary ethos. **The work of negotiation, disagreement, and adaptation recognised here is integral to living cultural heritage.**

Looking forward, the outcomes of D4.1 are not standalone. They will be carried into the practical domains of WP6, WP7, and WP8, where the challenge will be to embed this critical and theoretical sensitivity into designing digital infrastructures and AI-powered applications. The test of this framework will lie in its capacity to remain responsive to community perspectives, while also serving the project's broader goals of innovation, education, and sustainability.

10 Bibliography

- Appadurai, Arjun. 1988. "How to Make a National Cuisine: Cookbooks in Contemporary India." *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 30 (1): 3–24.
- Appadurai, Arjun. 1996. *Modernity At Large: Cultural Dimensions of Globalization*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Bator, Magdalena, and Marta Sylwanowicz. 2015. "Recipe, receipt and prescription in the history of English." *SELIM. Journal of the Spanish Society for Medieval English Language and Literature* 21: 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.17811/selim.21.2015.1-23>.
- Benjamin, Walter. 1968. "The Work of Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction." In *Illuminations: Essays and Reflections*. Schocken Books.
- Bijker, Wiebe E. 2012. "The Social Construction of Bakelite: Toward a Theory of Invention." In *The Social Construction of Technological Systems, Anniversary Edition: New Directions in the Sociology and History of Technology*. MIT Press.
- Bijker, Wiebe E., Thomas P. Hughes, and Trevor Pinch, eds. 1989. *The Social Construction of Technological Systems: New Directions in the Sociology and History of Technology*. MIT Press.
- Borghini, Andrea. 2015. "What Is a Recipe?" *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics* 28 (4): 719–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10806-015-9556-9>.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. 1984. *Distinction: A Social Critique of the Judgement of Taste*. Harvard University Press.
- Callon, Michel, Cécile Méadel, and Vololona Rabeharisoa. 2002. "The Economy of Qualities." *Economy and Society* 31 (2): 194–217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03085140220123126>
- Chakrabarty, Dipesh. 2000. *Provincializing Europe: Postcolonial Thought and Historical Difference*. Princeton University Press.
- Foucault, Michel. 1980. *Power/Knowledge: Selected Interviews and Other Writings, 1972–1977*. Pantheon Books.
- Foucault, Michel. 1989. *The Order of Things: An Archaeology of the Human Sciences*. Routledge.
- Garfinkel, Harold. 2023. "Studies in ethnomethodology." In *Social Theory Re-Wired*, edited by Wesley Longhofer and Daniel Winchester, 58–66. Routledge.
- GialloZafferano. n.d. *Fagiolini e patate con pesto alla Genovese e pistacchi*. Accessed June 4, 2025. <https://blog.giallozafferano.it/melacannellaefantasia/fagiolini-e-patate-con-pesto/>.
- Gieryn, Thomas F. 1983. "Boundary-Work and the Demarcation of Science from Non-Science: Strains and Interests in Professional Ideologies of Scientists." *American Sociological Review* 48 (6): 781–95. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095325>.
- Goody, Jack. 1982. *Cooking, Cuisine and Class: A Study in Comparative Sociology*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hutten, Ulrich von, Thomas Paynell, and Daniel Turner. 1730. *De Morbo Gallico: A Treatise of the French Disease, Publish'd above 200 Years Past*. With Francis A. Countway Library of Medicine. London: Printed for John Clarke at the Bible under the Royal Exchange. <http://archive.org/details/demorbogallicotr00hutt>.
- Knorr Cetina, Karin. 1999. *Epistemic Cultures: How the Sciences Make Knowledge*. Harvard University Press.

- Latour, Bruno. 1987. *Science in Action: How to Follow Scientists and Engineers Through Society*. Harvard University Press.
- Lawson, Nigella. 2007. *Nigella Express*. Chatto & Windus.
- Muñoz, Jose Esteban. 2006. "Ephemera as Evidence: Introductory Notes to Queer Acts." In *Visual Culture: Experiences in Visual Culture*, edited by Joanne Morra and Marquard Smith. Taylor & Francis.
- Oxford English Dictionary. n.d. *Recipe*. Accessed June 4, 2025.
https://www.oed.com/dictionary/recipe_n.
- Parasecoli, Fabio. 2022. *Gastronativism: Food, Identity, Politics*. Columbia University Press.
- Pinch, Trevor. 1996. "The Social Construction of Technology: A Review." In *Technological Change: Methods and Themes in the History of Technology*, edited by Robert Fox, 17–35. Routledge.
- Sacks, Harvey. 1995. *Lectures on conversation*. Vol. 1, edited by Gail Jefferson and Emanuel A. Schegloff, 289–331. Blackwell.
- Schneider, Rebecca. 2011. *Performing Remains: Art and War in Times of Theatrical Reenactment*. Routledge.
- Smith, Neil, dir. 1969. *Sesame Street*. Episode 0004, "One of These Things." Aired November 13, on National Educational Television.
- Spiller, Elizabeth. 2010. "Recipes for Knowledge: Maker's Knowledge Traditions, Paracelsian Recipes, and the Invention of the Cookbook, 1600–1660." In *Renaissance Food from Rabelais to Shakespeare*, edited by Joan Fitzpatrick, 55–72. Routledge.
- tavakoli, sahar. 2025. "Feeding People." PhD Dissertation, Cornell University.
<https://ecommons.cornell.edu/bitstreams/Oe6b119c-0d09-451e-abaf-36518b724f08/download>.

Annex I: Transcripts

The materials below consist of transcripts from interviews held with RELISH consortium leads. These are included as part of the report's output, providing direct insight into the range of perspectives that informed the framework.

Fillers (e.g., “um”), laughter, pauses, and moments of apparent incoherence have been retained in the transcription in keeping with ethnographic and ethnomethodological approaches to talk developed by scholars such as Harold Garfinkel (2023) and Harvey Sacks (1995). Following Garfinkel and Sacks, these features of speech are treated as analytically significant, revealing how participants organise meaning, manage turn-taking, display understanding, and negotiate social relationships in interaction.

Interviewee 01

st: Okay, so [redacted], we've just started the recording. Great.

IT0506: Thank you for the time, and I think maybe [redacted] will listen to these, and probably not too many other people. This is really for internal purposes. So the idea really is to start from how you see recipes in your field, and then maybe also the divisions that you see between your field and other fields, nearby fields, or also within the consortium in general; how you see so recipes in your field. And then we should talk on how to place that within the consortium maybe a little bit.

st: Ok and, uh, thank you so much [redacted] for taking the time and for this thing, I think that um, I think it's very important to uh, start with the ontology of the recipe—meaning the exploring what a recipe actually is, uh, who are or is the author of a recipe, the many formats and contexts of the action, uh, that, um, you know, give us the recipe as uh, and so on, so forth.

In terms of—you were asking me about the, uh, how this will, uh, sit in the...what we're doing with RELISH and I, I can provide my, um, *biased* maybe perspective. I think we have uh, um, it was supposed to be, and I think that would be very, very productive, we have a very composite group, meaning that um, there are the-the computing people, that are uh, respecting, are respecting some kind of data they can um, they can put...they can feed the machine on and elaborate on that data. Maybe not necessarily, add the...again, I don't wanna criticise anybody or, or...but not necessarily they have it, because is not, it's not their field, it's not what they usually do, maybe they have hundred percent uh, the quote, unquote *comprehension*, again of the multi form, multifarious way, uh, the, the, the culinary, gastronomic knowledge, uh, that recipes provide. Uh, but maybe, maybe they operate—also because it might be, might be easier, might be more, more productive for them—they operate starting um, from a concept of the recipe, like, I would say, like more, maybe, maybe nineteenth century Anglo-Protestant concept of what a recipe is. I mean some very specific, uh, again, culinary information uh, and guidelines

and direction to transform, transform ingredients in a, into, into a dish printed in some form of uh, uh, published stuff or, or preserved in archives and so on and so forth.

And so, a very—I'm gonna call it traditional, but traditional and super Western idea of what the recipe is. That excludes, for example, orality, uh, any, any recipes that can be, can be found in popular culture, or in personal any, any kind of uh, personal documents, from, from letters to autobiographies to uh, you know, hand written, uh, domestic, uh, cookbooks, and so on and so forth.

Then, then also, in terms of the dissemination of the uh, the end products, the end results of RELISH, I think we have, from the communication people—let's call it that way—we have an expectation that—and again, rightly so—an expectation that uh, uh, whatever we produce from our research would be also uh, um, ready to be consumed, ready to be used by, uh, the citizenry. So the, uh, the interested, ummm, consumer, people, cook, housewives, and so on so forth, through some kind of web platform—if I understand it—or apps connected to a, a web platform. Which means that—again—whatever, whatever, whatever we produce from our very individual researches, uh, is supposed also to be appealing to, attracting to, um, to the, um, let's say to a general audience, to the public and that, that they want to experiment and uh, on the recipes that we've, we've been working with.

So, in our specific case, or our work package is uh, is composed by, uh, uh, mostly historians, I would say, probably historians with no exceptions, uh, and, and um, so, I, I think probably our problem is that from, from our own, again, individual researches that I think now, at some point we have to socialise, uh, we probably, we have, we assume to, because we've been working with unknown recipes before, we have an understanding, an ontology of recipes, uh, we can even theorise about it, I'm not really sure, and I'm thinking about myself in the first place, I'm not sure if that's true. I mean I think we, uh, or, we should approach our own case studies, our own individual research, and uh, the recipes we'll be dealing with, with a more um, comprehensive and uh, insightful understanding uh, of the theory, not only the method, but also the theory of the recipe to, to produce something that is uh, innovative and uh, cutting edge, like we are supposed to do with a research project like RELISH

st: Great, no, no, no, good. So, we should zoom in—this is already very useful already, this thing with the distinctions, right? And um, and then I think in other conversations we mention also that there is this fact that, between the um simplification that is needed in the uh, data collection, machine analysis, and instead the complications, the, you know, the nuances that humanists study, and the people that are really studying intangible cultural heritage study, there is, there is also the need of realising tools, so something that is really acting for agency, like, for helping agency, that—

IT0506: Absolutely

st: There are a few topics, let's go from the most specific to then, maybe then more general. The more specific is...I would like to see, in your field, right; so the research that you're doing for RELISH, and maybe also other research that is related, you know there is an overlap, how the

recipe is conceived. So in that in the historical periods that you are considering that are relatively recent, you know, in a sense, and how it is conceived there, and how the different, uh, ways of thinking of recipes that you were mentioning, you know, the oral history, letters, private, um, communication. How, how do they feature? You know, how recipes can be featured there? How is it that you—what kind of tools you use to capture them and record them or detect the presence of a recipe? And then how then you have seen evolutions, you know, differences?

IT0506: Right. So, this is my particular, uh, particular ah, ah, case study or whatever, my particular [inaudible] with very tentative—I have, I have, unfortunately I have nothing written yet uh, [inaudible] you know, get your comment and feedback. So, uh, I, I start from a very concrete and very actual, very actual event, which is being, being contracted a few months ago to the, the, the magazine that the what is supposed to be the most. what is supposed to be the most historical food magazine, culinary magazine Italy, *La Cucina*, set to be published in 1929 uh, this, this important, because the, the founder of *Cucina Italiana* was a fascist leader uh, uh, uh, of the first hour and from the title of *Cucina Italiana*, you immediately think of something that is very national, nationalistic and centralistic and uh, uh, uh, and so on and so forth.

With the, the, the, you know, very, very much reverberation of the power of the state, which is really what was the case, at least that before World War Two, with, with, with the magazine. Anyway, I was contacted by this, this magazine because the, um, the mini *aspetta*— basically, what is the, what would be the Department of State, of the Department of Foreign Affairs in Italy, was promoting in tandem with the Ministry Department of Agriculture, which is now called the Department of Agriculture and Food Sovereignty—another important terminology, uh, was and is working on ah, um, an application for recognising the Italian cuisine, Italian food and Italian cuisine and human, UNESCO human heritage. So there sat on uh, um, the making heritagisation of Italian and Italian cuisine as being internationally recognised, as being for the ultimate, ultimate purpose of basically patent what Italian food, Italian cuisine, really are, and valorise it, and uh, valorise it in the world with this extra... patrimonialised it, and valorised it with the extra label of uh, um, uh, world, world human heritage, and uh, uh, so I immediately thought of RELISH since, you know, we're talking about, uh, recipes and gastronomy as uh, cultural heritage, this would be a perfect example of, uh, that is eventually ongoing and but the, the important uh, um, what was really important was that they contacted me—I've been studying the, the foodways of Italian migrants in the, in the great diaspora since the...Italian diaspora since the nineteenth century, with a particular focus on the United States but in general, uh, and basically, the um, uh, the, the, the ministries, the magazine asked me for a set of uh, recipes, they call it the, they wanted to call it the 'Recipes of Memory' uh, recipes basically elaborated by Italian migrants who circulate around the world or circulated within the Italian diaspora in the last, almost, uh, little more than one hundred and fifty years.

Okay, I think, uh, their ultimate purpose is to say that, uh, even Italians abroad, even through the generations, all these millions of people have a, maintained a strong sense of affiliation with homeland, um, um, through food—food was a, was a, major, major media of um, a sense of belonging, of affiliation, again continuing through the generation of, of, of the people, even

people born abroad, with the sense of, also a strong sense of *nostalgia* [laughter] even nostalgia from a past that they never lived, actually, in reality in actuality.

So both, I think the ultimate goal, is to make these something valuable, both in terms, both in terms of the economy of Italy...I mean, the export of food and wine is a unbelievably important item in Italian international trade and Italian economy as all, but also in terms of political terms, you know that that it is important that uh, uh, these connection going into through, though the generations is uh, uh, is kept and valorised for diplomatic uses, diplomatic reason in general, to, to strengthen the sense, the sense of uh, uh, belonging to the Italian, to an Italian nation, which is more global than ever.

If you, if you think, if you think about it, also the fact that uh, um, Italy...immigration policy in Italy follow strictly, follow the rule of the uh, uh, uh, *jus sanguinis*, not *jus soli*, meaning that now they restrict, they restricted [inaudible]. But even if your great, great parent was born in Italy, and you, your, your parents lived in Argentina, Brazil, Australia, Canada, the United States, paying taxes always to these countries and not, not to Italy. You're still part of the Italian nation, because there is this broad link, uh, uh, you know, continuing through time and space, uh, so.

This, I think is their, is their proposal which [inaudible] they are just reporting, uh, uh, with for, from my angle, for somebody who started working on, on this topic forty years ago, when the, the basically food studies was basically non-existent as a, as a field, as a concept, there was very, very little also about food history in general, but certainly nothing about what immigrants of any country, any...ate and ated, so it was kind of, it was kind of surprising, you know, there had been really, a revolution. So, uh, so important we never did food, in thinking about food, uh, also the legitimation of the field so far, which you know, has gone so far to even embrace uh, you know, the mostly illiterate um mostly women immigrant cooks of the late nineteenth century, early twentieth century, uh, like the heroes of the story instead of somebody that history has not recorded, not valuable, so it was, uh, it was really big.

So, I was interested in uh, the realising this revolution happening, and so, yeah, so basically, I would like to work on this thing. Now, second part of your question—you want to say something on this or I can—talking about the sources and--

st: No, this is very interesting so, I mean, what is interesting here is there seems to be a need for actually, *identities* through recipes, so this would have to be shared. So what I'm curious, and think could be relevant also for the grant, for the report that we have to do, and thinking just of this discussion within the consortium is, it gives, there is a reason for, uh, in this case the Italian government and for making the cases in front of UNESCO for unification, but then I'm curious to see, what are the signs of unity. I imagine if they were linguistic, identity, like the same names, or uh, the same uh, because I imagine the procedures, if you have people who have migrated in different countries, maybe in one case they use the tub, in another case they use a bucket, and, you know--

IT0506: Absolutely

st: And the tomatoes are, you know, salt is not the same, oil—so I'm curious how you find unity in difference, in different countries, in the examples that you are um, that you, and also difference in media for transmission of recipes, as you were mentioning.

IT0506: Right. Okay. In terms of, in terms of unity, uh, in terms of unity, this is, this is what um, this is what, what, one of the many reasons why, why I study the Italian diaspora, um, it basically, it not, it not only the number, the size of immigration—between 1876 when the Italian state, which was a new nation state, in other words, just fifteen uh, uh, fifteen years old, fifteen: one five—start uh, collecting the applications for passport for uh, uh, international immigration, and 1876 was the first time the trade—*the trade paths*—the *migration* balance between people entering and leaving the country turn into positive: there were more people, more people coming into Italy rather than leaving, twenty seven million Italians left the country, so that's the, the, *entire* population of Italy at the time of unification in 1861, it's like one entire country.

And, what is, sorry, pretty, pretty unique. The, uh, the um, *come si chiama*, the, hm, *sì*, *no*: the other important thing is... two others:

One is that most of these people, until the fifties and sixties, now they changed significantly but for a good century, two thirds of the, the people who immigrated were men, single men. They went where, where, wherever they were going with the intention, many of them with the intention to return to Italy so that, that's um, some of them didn't, they sent for the rest of their families, their spouses and for girlfriend and servant too...so...so there was always the circulation of people also foods, ideas, taste, so on, so forth, basically it never stopped because people went back and forth a lot, um, but there's, but there's also another aspect relative to that which is that this, this, these many single men—wherever they went; Germany, Switzerland, where ever—they need, they needed to be fed and most of the time they, they, they, they uh, had their meals, three meals a day or...on the construction, uh, uh, camps, or mining camps, or, or living together, living together maybe ten or a couple of rooms, and there was always women for the most part cooking for them, uh, basically the idea of the uh, uh, collective uh, um, *come si dice*, so, you know, the fact that Italian restaurants are so widespread everywhere started with the fact that there were all these immigrants that also—I was born in Turin in 1963 and I remember people mostly from the south of Italy, in the seventies, they, uh, they went to this very, the same formal restaurants and they had, uh, they had their meals together, um, so that thing, that's another important thing to be considered.

Uh, the third thing to be considered, perhaps the most important, is that Italians went everywhere. At different times in history, they went to different places. Millions, nearly three and a half million went to the United States at the turn of the twentieth century, when, in 1924 the US Congress passed the first, uh, big immigration act which were ninety percent aimed at excluding them, especially southern Italians, they just found another destination after World War Two, even, uh, not only Germany, Switzerland, France, so on and so forth, or Belgium, but also places like Canada, Australia, so on and so forth. So, everywhere.

So, I think this, I think the difference for Turks in Germany, ninety percent of Turkish immigrants went to Germany, Mexicans to the United States, Italians are a different, different kind, different kind of migrants. So I think, again, the Department of State, uh, think of that, or the Department of International Trade, how it's called, also Made in Italy, Department of Made in Italy so on and so forth, think in terms of, you know, turning uh, these Italian traces around the world into value, they also consider the fact that, uh, basically, there is a diplomatic representation made in migrants, first, second, third, fourth generation really around the world. So, they...and they think in terms of unity, like you say, like any kind of nationalistic leader [laughter] have been doing for a good century. Meaning that another characteristic of Italian migration is to be—not only Italian migration really, it is not a, it is not an *exception* in that way—but specifically, this also because the Italian nation state was so young, these people were part of a so-called village outreach migration, meaning, meaning when they left, they village where...my father was born in a village where ninety percent of the people self-immigrated to the United States between 1904 and 1908, right before World War One, really, now in fact it's a ghost town, and there are many more [redacted] in the United States than in Italy, much, many, many, many more. Um, they, they left this place—which by the way it is called Canischio, it is a tiny place, *horrible place* on the alps—uh, they, they were farmers, they came to the United States they became miners, okay? But their sense of affiliation and belonging was not with the Italian state which was, the face of the Italian state for them was the tax collector and uh, um, maybe the school teacher who teaching them all the glories of the Italian past and so on so forth, and, and, uh, the army that uh, that [inaudible] drafting [inaudible] taking away two important arms to work on the farm, so [inaudible] and the same thing was true for...so.

What were the recipes that travelled with these people? They were not what you could find in Artusi or, or Ada Boni later, you know, the *culinary knowledge*—and completely unwritten—not completely, mostly unwritten, that travelled with them in their brains and then they, they tried to recreate in a completely different [inaudible]

[Recording cuts]

Interviewee 02

IT2201: Oh, right. All right.

st: Uh, so when we last spoke, we spoke mostly about recipes, and I wanted to follow up, to ask, I guess, about intangible cultural heritage.

IT2201: Right, yes.

st: Um, uh, and the notion of a *database* of intangible cultural heritage is itself kind of um, a nifty thing, because a database implies some sort of codifiability and intangibility itself implies uncodifiability.

IT2201: Yes.

st: So it leads me to want to ask, from your professional—or, if you want personal, I don't I don't mind either way—perspective, what do you think should really guide the way we engage with the intangible?

IT2201: Yeah. It's a very good question and, and actually, I feel like, um, these...catching up, after the conversation we had is actually quite, um, what's the word I'm looking for? It's actually quite good because since then, I've had the chance of, oh, yeah; that I actually had the experience of engaging with some of these ideas of heritage in terms of food and recipes in real life as part of our project.

So, um, just basically giving you the background is that, um, as part of this idea of, uh, recipes and tracing recipes and thinking about, uh, one of the phrases that we use is that recipes *illuminate* the world that they come from, right? So that illumination can be sort of historical in the present, but it could be also in the past. Yeah. Um, so one of the things that happened for RELISH was that um, one of the plan activities, which was a comparison or a comparison cooking of two recipes. Uh, the Arabic السكبيج and the escabetx from the Catalan sort of medieval uh, recipe collection, because it seemed to share a common element, uh, our partners wanted to try together and sort of figure out competing comparative notes and so on.

So this activity got canceled for other reasons. Uh, but our partners in, um, Fundació Alícia decided to use the time that they had already had in reserve for this activity, and instead they tried to say, *okay, this dish that we were going to compare with the Arabic medieval manuscript, we actually do not know that much about this dish.*

And it has a long history because it is a dish that is still eaten today, is still made today. Uh, it comes from a manuscript from the 1300s. Uh, the oldest manuscript uh, in the Iberian Peninsula, the *Sent Soví*, uh, that gives a very succinct kind of description that says if you want to make escabetx, do *this*.

But in a way, the recipe doesn't tell us anything. It only tells that it has fish, it has almond milk, it has bread, it has some sugar and salt, and it has vinegar. It doesn't give you quantities, doesn't give you steps, doesn't give you really anything.

Um, So we tried, so our partners kind of mapped out this recipe and they decided what are the ingredients, what are some of the steps, what are what they call vital codes or optional codes? And would be a, um, something called intuitive cooking.

So we divided in three teams and we kind of interpreted that recipe. With the same ingredients, but no instructions, so we divided ourselves into teams, in three teams, sorry, and we tried it. And would produce uh, three dishes that were completely different from each other. Um, they had the same ingredients, but they looked different. They tasted different.

Um, and our understanding of it was very different and our own approach to it...actually [redacted] just wrote a post on it so you can kind of follow that.

And it was quite surprising because in the tasting, We didn't have kind of a reference to what they should taste like. So we kind of came up with these dishes to our best understanding. And we had no idea what we were supposed to taste. So, in that way, you are kind of recreating the past. This is part of your kind of culinary heritage, I guess. And you kind of think about these

recipes as that connection, uh, between time, between cultural... but our faith in that kind of transcription or that kind of documentation is just so limited, right?

st: Yeah.

IT2201: Um, in the sense that, in fact, even though it's written, it just does not communicate what we need to know because experience, taste, or that moment of living where when they said fish, it could only mean these, you know, certain amount of fish, but we don't know if it is a blue fish, if it's a white fish, if it's a river fish. You know, like we have no idea of anything.

Um, in fact, the only thing that we know, I know is, um, so the depth that they could fish from would eliminate a certain amount of fish, but, you know, kind of those limited guesses as well. But anyway, sort of—the thinking about the limitations of our understanding of the past.

And actually, the illusion that we have, that we have a connection with the past, was actually a very humbling experience because we cooked a lot, we tried a lot. We guessed a lot. We speculated a lot, yet at the end of the day, we all ended up saying, *but we don't know*.

st: Yeah. Yeah, yeah.

IT2201: You know?

st: Yeah.

IT2201: And in that, it kind of made me think about, you know, like those videos right now that are going around social platforms saying, you know, young people asking their mothers or grandmothers for a recipe. And getting these very approximate recipes, like put a little bit of this, put a little bit of that, you know. And they say, I don't know what, you'd get to give me measurements. It's like, I don't know, just, you know, like one funny phrase that I heard was, you know, the, the, *the pan will keep you asking*. You know, how much flour or liquid they should go into, right? So then they make for us like, *what the hell*, you know, *when is the pan starting to, is going to start talking to me*, okay? Taking it literally what the mother is instructing.

But it was interesting to think about that these young people trying to get sort of a transcript of what they consider to be part of their culinary tradition and what they miss or might not have the culinary knowledge nor the technique to reproduce what they want to eat. But they hold the knowledge of taste. They know what they're going after, right? A Milanese; whatever it is that they're eating.

On the other hand, in our experiment, we have a lot of culinary knowledge. I mean, it was a team made up by professional chefs. Uh, chefs who specialise in history. They knew a lot of things about the culinary world, the, you know, like knowledge. Yet, none had the experience and knowledge of what this dish should taste like.

st: Yeah.

IT2201: So, in that sense, you know, um, I mean, there were other topics that came out. out of this experience, like, uh, does that mean that not giving instructions makes it future proof? Because you can do anything you want with that recipe, which is what we ended up doing. Uh, or, if you actually give very detailed instructions about a recipe, does this means that you can kind of like freeze that moment and that's more sort of like a, a museum piece, right? That

might not actually be able to be repeated because soon we're not gonna have fish and we're not gonna have almonds. We're not gonna have electricity. I don't know. Right?

Um, So it was an interesting thing. So we've seen those boundaries of limitations. When you think about heritage as something desirable. And something that is worth preserving, perhaps, then the trickiest and more difficult question is what is it actually that you're trying to preserve? Or what *can* you preserve? And in this desire for preservation, perhaps what you are doing is not so much about actual preservation. But you're engaging in a moment of negotiation in which you're trying to understand what is valuable at your present moment.

St: Yeah.

IT2201: Um, so culinarily speaking, it was interesting because we very soon engage in questions of taste, right? And it was, *this tastes good to me, this tastes bad to me*. But then even that was kind of a fraught discussion because depending on your own culinary tradition and experience, you are more tolerant of sour, you know, flavours compared to sweet and so on, right?

Um, so then to, kind of, you know, find that middle ground in which, okay, this is the version that we all could live with, you know, that happy medium. Uh, that also then we kind of threw out the window, this idea of, you know, authenticity or, I mean, we just couldn't, you know, like, reach an agreement, right? Because we don't know.

st: Yeah.

IT2201: Um. So, yeah, so heritage in that sense, I mean, and there's been plenty written about this, right? At this point it's an ideal. It's, you know, it's, it's, it's impossible. Um, and perhaps you can think, *oh, but a museum or a piece of sculpture or an archaeological site, something that is concrete and material, that you preserve*. And perhaps those are material traces left. But you still cannot *really* engage with what the context was because it has been lost through time and through just generational laws, right?

st: Yeah.

IT2201: I came to realise that. Um, and I think that in terms of, cooking and dishes and ingredients and recipes. Uh, it is still, it is exactly that, but it's a lot more fleeting and it's a lot more complicated. Because I think subjectivity and sort of that that culture that you bring into, uh, the act of eating and the way your taste buds, you know—or your own experience of eating food and what you enjoy, what you don't—is so subjective, right?

st: Yeah.

IT2201: So it's a big ask, right? When you think about heritage negotiation on food that was eaten in the past, I've come to realise now. Um, yeah. So I think then. Perhaps what we need to understand or come to terms with is that when you think about heritage, it's not so much about valuing or preserving the past or your tradition. But rather, you're creating a space where you kind of have to come to terms with the moment where you exist and what are you negotiating with, with whom and what, and what values you're putting forth, right?

st: Yeah, yeah.

IT2201: So there is no single answer, but I think it's a lot more complicated that, that, that, than we initially thought, perhaps? And I think that, um, the more you read about heritage and the scholarly work that is being produced about heritage, is that heritage is pretty much anything you make it to be, and at the same time it's nothing. So if that is the case, then it ceases to be a useful either framework or concept. I mean, you're a philosopher, you know a lot more.

st: I'm not a... Unfortunately, I'm not a philosopher.

IT2201: But you play with philosophers.

st: I'm an interloper, maybe.

IT2201: Okay, you are more loyal of this. But anyway, so that's kind of where I'm where I'm at. So I'm finding that heritage. Kinda gives you a framework, I guess. Um, sort of a boundary. But it's not... the more you think about it, the less of a kind of guiding principle of a critical insight it is, right? It's not a critical lens anymore. Uh, so perhaps it's more of a tool. It will be an instrument. Uh, and not so much about to understand the past, but kind of, to take an assessment of your present. In what kind of negotiations you have to enter; to find value in a common practice that you want to take forward.

st: Yeah, like an historiography of heritage studies?

IT2201: Yes, exactly. So I feel like heritage is no longer or it shouldn't be past facing, but rather is future facing. But not in the sense of preserving for the future. But rather, in a conversation that makes a future. Right? Because I think that whatever you're preserving, or whatever existed in the past, eventually loses value, right? I mean, so you have to make...you have you have to make value, you have to find meaning to make it valuable and that producing of value—it's, it's a cultural negotiation. right? And clearly then all the competing interests, all the institutions, where is it top down? Is it bottoms up? Who gets involved? Who are the stakeholders? All of those things are coming to play as well, right?

Um, so yeah, um, the morning I engaged with it, the more sort of, almost it becomes like fun time massacreing, right? Like, it's a sampling, you know, like, we're kind of, um, pursuing it, but, um, in what ways has the way that we understood heritage to be, is more about not preserving the future, but actually creating paths of living towards, you know, not, not preserving the past or the future, but rather, how you actually make living conditions for the future. Does that make sense?

st: It makes sense. It's a, it's a bit of a less sinister version of the Orwell *controlling the past as controlling the future*.

IT2201: Right. I think there is a version of that, that clearly you create these views and there's definitely a continuation of hegemonic, you know, sort of ways of seeing, understanding life. I think that definitely is at play. And I think that heritage in that sense is top down, is, you know, sinister and I'm not, I mean, even the grant that we're engaged in, in a way, will get plagued by these forces, right? But at the same time, at sort of the ground level where you are actually engaging in this kind of work, minute as it, as it is, because what we did is, it doesn't even count as anything, right? We just, you know; a bunch of people got together to kind of *play* basically, right? But you need a very brief moment—

st: You feel that? You feel that you feel that's not anything? Because it is something.

IT2201: It is something. Obviously. I mean, we got...it took lots amount of time, resources. We spent a lot of money, time, you know, effort and all of those things, that's absolutely real. But in the in the in the realm of things, I think it is a very minor thing. But it is extraordinary that in those contact points, you actually come with these moments of insight and perhaps not so much of clarity, but of confusion, right?

st: Yeah.

IT2201: Um, that makes you kind of rethink what you're being kind of...in terms of what are you actually valuing in heritage? Why do you want to preserve? Why do you want to have heritage? Right? Um, and I've always had this feeling that the connotation of the word, both in practice, was trying to instrumentalise something static, for economic, you know, interest or what, you know, come and see our heritage, buildings, you know, tourism, and... um, but I'm starting to wonder if this conversation is, um, about heritage, um, they can be instrumentalised in a different way, right? Or they're actually tools that should not be there...tools that, yes, they are used that way, but that can also serve other purposes, or at least we're using them, um, to create a different kind of experience and knowledge, right? Um, and it feels a lot, that the heritage is not so much the product, right? Or is it the doing?

st: Yeah. Yeah, yeah. As you're describing the experience of working through this recipe and and not having these quantities and trying to...as you spoke about the fish, and you talked about how, okay, well, there are some things that we can keep in mind; not having the name of the fish, encourages us to think about depths and so on. And it made me think of, um, have you read—I'm sure you have—Carlo Ginsberg's *The Cheese and the Worms* or, more, his piece on *The Clue*, and these, like...

IT2201: No, I actually have not.

st: Or, or it also, I guess, it made me think of—I don't know, this might be apocryphal, but early modern drawings of animals from other continents that were based off of descriptions and come out janky.

IT2201: Yeah, yeah, yeah. Like in the colonial world, those, yeah, archives and the codexes. and yeah, yeah, absolutely.

st: Yeah. And so if what we want to capture is not just heritage, but this idea of the tangible containing the intangible. Does the struggle itself become a way of engaging with an experience of the past? Because it seems that in the past, people also had this problem of, *I don't know what to do with this. Is this what it's meant to be? Is this a rhino? Who's to say?*

IT2201: Yeah. I think that's it. So perhaps, you know, our desire to think about heritage, intangible character is that you want to express it concretely through something, even though we talk about intangible culture, it adapts. It is a dish. It is, right? So it's something that you can identify quickly. And it represents something for a community or a place or whatever. So I think that even though they use the word intangible, there is this tension in which in order to make it intangible and valuable, you have to make it tangible, right? That, that, that, that tension. Um, and perhaps what the intangibility should highlight is the negotiation that has to go into making it tangible. So, for example, thinking about the early maps of the colonial, you know, world, uh, when they say, *okay, these are maps* and then the indigenous people say, *okay, there are*

people. So, you know, you can't just put, you know, a two-dimensional map, but you have to put footprints, right? All the, all the maps, footprints, you know, um, of people walking from point A to point B, and uh, some cartographers of the time are even, even so more detailed that not only they understand that people walk, but animals go with them, so you have footprints of animals and people walking. Right? So they're kind of, okay, you have to represent, so they're like trying to merge their own understanding of space and illustration onto sort of the logos of the Western world and the way they think about cartography.

So perhaps that's what happens, right? So when you think about, okay, *this is an intangible culture of this region*, you have to come up with this representation, intangibility that people can identify, recognise value, and whatever. But then what is useful in that is in the negotiation that goes in the production of the tangible thing, right? At the end of the tangible thing, is it's not going to be the same for anyone, right? So you're not going to make the perfect carbonara or you're not going to make them whatever it is, um, and even if you go and have, this is, yeah, so in time, like dance, music, whatever, that is intangible. But even intangible culture has this representation, and they're so varied at the end of the day, that thing, that the intangible culture produces, it's not—it can change, right? It, it, it, it's not fixed. Um. So, perhaps, it's in the process from intangible to tangible, that intangible culture needs tangibility and it is that process of conversation that, it illuminates or it creates some insight about the differences in temporality, perhaps.

It was really interesting because I had no idea when we're talking about the fish, you know. Um, it says, take the fish, and then, but one fish, we don't know, you know, and then they're like, okay, we know for sure that they could only fish up to this depth. Yeah. that takes away: it couldn't have been tuna, it couldn't have been, you know, suddenly there are all these fishes that are out of the equation. I have no knowledge of that, right? So it was interesting, all sort of these deductions that you have to do, is like quite a logical process, right? In which, um, you are arriving to a possible version of a recipe that will allow you to plausibly recreate something that you have no idea how it should taste like.

st: Yeah, yeah. I mean, the fish gets even more complicated if we think about things like—so there's a Sicilian dish that is named after a kind of songbird, but is made out of fish, because those somebirds are difficult to get, and you can kind of replicate the flavour with fish, or mince pies of at one point had minced meat in them.

IT2201: Right.

st: And now they...so it could, the escabete could also just not have fish. Not to make things worse, but...

IT2201: Yeah, so it was also interesting in that sense because some of the more sort of, the like, the history specialists in the group doing the cooking, there were also chefs or cooks. We're constantly repeating this mantra, which at IT2201t didn't kind of, I didn't understand it, but, um, and then I kind of got thinking about it was, *a dish doesn't make a name and a name does not make a dish*. So it's almost like this has to, you know, de Saussure.

st: [laughter] Right

IT2201: This is how, you know, if you go into the signifier and the signified and all that, right? Um, you know, thinking about my 90s education [laughter]. But I think that there is something to it, like how mince pies become like that, no? There's no mince meat, or, like, why like this is bird dish, it's fish, but it's shaped like a bird, you know? Like, so... but we kind of lost all of the, the, the, the story around it, right?

Um, and I think that, To think that we can recover that, that, that history or the context. Um, seems um, quite arrogant, I have to say, from our part. I'm thinking we have way too much faith in our own, I know, methods and research and capacities and stuff, but, um, I think with time, there is just irrevocable loss, right? There is no way of recovering that.

st: Yeah.

IT2201: So, faced with that absolute loss because it is absolutely no way, right? How do you cope with it and what kind of negotiations you engage with is what makes me think about what we do with intangible heritage or intangible culture today, right?

st: Yeah. Well, this point on negotiation and heritage and intangible culture, kind of leads nicely to my last question, which is gonna be poorly articulated.

But, in talking about...how you mentioned earlier that, in order to capture the intangible, we need to make it at least partially tangible. But presumably we don't want to completely mIT2201epresent it. We don't want to change its form. So are there aspects of this transformation that you would like to see in our own platform signposted to be avoided? Like, *do not do this in your rendering of one into the other...*

IT2201: Yeah, I think that, that in that process, right, I mean, so, again, when I talked about this example of, like, escabetx, and when we came to tasting, we all had to kind of agree on a profile of taste and we thought, we'll make this again. That is no good. Or that way too much. And the group was constantly divided, right? And depending who was the loudest, who in the group seemed to hold, you know, uh, there was definitely hierarchy, right? Because they were junior cooks and they were more senior people.

Yeah. So all that was kind of a very diplomatic dance going on there. Um, so when you arrive to kind of a consensus, there is a lot of things being lost there, right? So perhaps, In that process of making intangible into a tangible, That is as inclusive as it could be. We should also recognise those limitations, right?

st: Yeah.

IT2201: So I guess what I'm trying to say is, It's not that it's a lost cause. to kind of engage in this exercise. But perhaps our focus on the final product is not the right way to go about it. I think that at the end of the day, What we thought engaging in this was, oh, we're going to find the correct recipe to produce x or we're going to taste something totally different, which we did. But we don't know in what kind of approximation. But everybody that was involved in that exercise, in that, in that process of making this abstract thing, that was part of culinary culture that is present today in their plates in very different ways.

Um, we all went within with certain expectations than we all came out, I think, not with one view about this, but with very different insights, because in each phase of what we did, um, it

created different moments of understanding for a lot of us. So, I think that, that it, that's why suddenly I'm thinking, oh, it's a process that is more important than what you arrive to, right? Um, [redacted] will tell you that she created this huge *blendergate* in the process of, um, of doing this. She writes about it in the piece. Um, but yeah, so it's like it, it, it doesn't fit in a box. I feel like, but everything that we're trying to do is, okay, how we're going to articulate this idea, how we're gonna make it, you know, fit into this box, how we're gonna explain x and part of our past in this project is precisely to articulate this experience. And I'm sure that we'll get into trouble if the conclusion of what we say in our reports, deliverables is, *but we don't know*.

st: Yeah.

IT2201: You know, so we have to produce some sort of knowledge. Um, so I'm thinking that perhaps the knowledge then is not kind of the end product, but its *how do we create a framework or a methodology that allows to pay more attention to what kind of negotiations and processes are taking place when you start talking about intangible culture and you can agree to what you arrive at*.

st: Yeah.

IT2201: But that, And, you know, I mean, it feels very abstract and like uh, kind of all of these very, these unsatisfying humanities kind of like. question and answers [laughter].

st: [Laughter] Well I think a level of abstractness is permissible when we're talking about the intangible. If it were not abstract, we're no longer talking about the intangible. We just talking about archiving: we're just talking about old-fashioned, classico archiving—like, by an Archon.

IT2201: Yes, exactly. *We're going to pick this manuscript*. Exactly. And perhaps that's what it is. Like, somebody kept the manuscript, the sensory, and they said, we're preserving something. And then we take that archive and doing something totally different with it, right? Like, we're trying to cook it, we're trying to dialogue with it, we're trying to make it work. Yeah. Or trying to make it talk to us and it's not just this flat thing, you know, I don't know, that says no...

st: That has no footprints.

IT2201: Yeah, exactly. Yeah. Um, so the abstraction part, yeah, I totally get your point. But I think that in the way that we address, we address that abstraction, in the vocabulary that we have, in the concepts that we rely on to express this kind of ambivalence and confusion. I think that that the audience for that, is, is very, will not understand, right? Because unfortunately, a lot of the audience for...what they want is very institutional, it's very, I don't know, you know; people don't like engaging in abstraction. They want things to be white or black, good or bad. You know?

st: I have faith in the in the young people. Uh, they; I really, I enjoy how, how woke the young people are. I think they do want to look at a recipe and say, something like, *well, no, this recipe only looks like this because of colonialism, and I reject that, and I reject the idea of a single recipe because who was the person who wrote it, and I want a more, um, I want more vantages, I want an agonistic approach to recipes*, you know, like, I think the kids are like that. The kids love to get political on the internet

IT2201: Yeah, yeah, I agree. I actually had the opportunity to spend three weeks with my nephew who's 25. I hadn't seen him in a very long time. I certainly had no experience interacting with him as a young adult. Uh, and from the time that I'd last seen him, he's become

a good cook and very interested in food. And I was very, not only impressed by his knowledge and what his aspirations were, but very interested in the way that he engaged with culinary knowledge and information out there. Like the way that he read or dIT2201egarded a recipe, who he followed, what kind of videos he liked or not? Uh, and kind of one of the things that made me think about is that, I, I, I also feel like we're in that, shift—epistemologically speaking—in which, I think I was brought up in a moment in which, in order to cook, well, you have to follow recipes, you know; if they said two centimeters, I would get my ruler to check two centimeters. Martha Stewart was the goddess and whatever she did, I did everything she said.

st: You did insider trading? You did white collar crime?

IT2201: I should have followed there, I could have been rich.

st: [laughter]

IT2201: Um, but like, like, my, my nephew, follows certain things, but also the kind of cooking that he and his friends seem to do or the young people seem to do, is a lot more intuitive. Yeah. Yeah. And they go by what they want, by they want to eat. But they find it, you know, speaks to them in terms of appetite and whatever, and they have absolute dIT2201egard for other things, which I found it very interesting.

But at the same time, just rule by appetite, and, you know, also, it's really challenging in terms of, you know, when we think about sustainability, responsible eating, and, you know. So I found that kind of conflict. They're not completed. I mean, I think that he is, in the case of my nephew, I think that he understands, you know, local food, seasonality, and all that. Um, but even sort of the richness of the information out there, you know, his own financial situation. It like the accessibility of things or the capacity for, uh, for consuming a vast amount of products, that's quite shocking, right?

st: Yeah. Yeah.

IT2201: Anyway.

st: Uh, that's it for all of my questions. Is there anything you want to... get on record?

IT2201: Um, yeah, maybe, maybe we should think about, you know, what this project has taught us about. Thinking about cooking and recipes as both intangible and tangible culture, right? Because in a way, we're engaging with both sides of what we understand as heritage, right? Intangible because we kind of value something that we keep doing, it's not fixing time. But tangible again in these manifestations of the recipes or something that can be preserved, can be recorded, and that. And what we discover in this project is that we're constantly in between. Right? And what we're finding um, valuable, at least for us in terms of gaining understanding and insight about uh, culinary culture, is in this transition between the intangible, to the tangible, right? So it's not so much about the recipe *per se*, but what happens in that process of getting to that recipe.

st: Right. Yeah.

IT2201: Yeah.

st: Well, thank you.

IT2201: So in that sense, like, I don't know what kind of critical framework do we need to, you know, unpack this, right? That's for package 4?

st: Yeah, no, I'm trying. I'm trying. I'm doing my best. And I'm grateful for the feedback. Yeah, thank you.

IT2201: No, so it was really fascinating. I have to say that I didn't expect to have so much fun and um, participating in, in a cooking kind of workshop plan.

st: No, it sounds really rad.

IT2201: Yeah, also interesting. Very humbling too.

st: Um, all right. Well, I will, I've taken enough of your time. I will let you go for the evening.

IT2201: Okay, thank you. Um, I'm gonna go to [redacted], actually talk, um, she's giving about food memories.

st: Oh, please tell her I said hello.

IT2201: All right.

st: Okay. Thank you, ciao ciao.

IT2201: All right, ciao.

Interviewee 03

IF2301: Right, substance. Let's start from that. You start recording and I'll say *whatever provides substance*.

st: Okay, sounds good. So, when we've spoken in previous occasions, we've mostly talked about recipes, but—

IF2301: Are you recording?

st: I am recording.

IF2301: Okay, good, good.

st: But what I'd like to ask you about today is less about recipes and more about intangibility and intangible culture, because what we're doing in a sense is creating a codified database of uncodifiable practice; movement, you know, the ephemeral, the ineffable, you often use the word ineffable. Um, So, I suppose my first question for you, is from your particular disciplinary vantage, are there certain considerations of intangibility that you think should be maintained as we approach this larger project of RELISH?

IF2301: Hmm. I mean, this is a huge question. I don't know. I think, so I can say, let me see how we could say something here that there could be, it could make sense.

So there is, I'd say that there is a part of the... of the intangibility that, um, that I think can be is often, you know, also used and then make more explicit, let's say, by actually— references even to material objects that enable it, right? So I don't know if that's the easiest part of the intangibility, but there is depth.

And even a practice that is intangible, but is made possible through, you know, a cup, a mug, whatever, with certain...some tools. So you have a lot, I think, of studies—even of heritage, even intangible heritage—you might look at tools at places, spaces that enable whatever intangible norms, practices, habits, it might be, right?

And even within probably STS, social anthropology, parts of philosophy, there's so many disciplines, right? They might look at these. And probably also, if we think about when we study the ancient, so to speak, societies, communities, through the objects, we try to uncover intangible practices, right? So how are the, I don't know, the Babylonians eating? Well, maybe we look at the objects, and we try the spaces, and we try to imagine what kind of practices they were at, what was a bench, but how they were sitting, however.

I think that is... so I'm quite fascinated in the link, the sense I think there is, it's interesting also if you take the philosophy or the ontology, that's in part, for instance, what we try to do with the spaces, you know, the gastrospace, whatever. So you think you look at some material aspects of a space, whatever is material, physical, whatever you want. And then we think how those conditions enable maybe some precisely practices, you know, ways of being together or or, you know, acting, cooking, whatever, parting that. So that's one part. Um, and I, it's, um, So you can start from there.

I don't know. I think that for me, it's agreeing, um, an obvious point because it's used even in museums in a lot of places and a lot of places. That is another part to intangibility, and there is perhaps one that from my perspective, for example, in certain exercises—things you have done or written, you were also emphasising... very lightly so—and it's sort of that which is implicit, you know? And it has to deal with, as you want to call it, knowledge, there is tacit. But it's not even that. They're just that implicit aspects, right? And those, I don't think that some of those implicit aspects, that, like, increasing rules in every, you know, code within a community of norms.

Um, It's not about how you find the link between the, you know, the behavior and the material culture, it's not that. Because even once you found the link, you're still looking so to speak at visible pigs. You're thinking there is a behavior. I see, you know, [redacted] drinking like *this*, you know, or sipping the tea in a certain way, whatever, cooking, or and then you have precise, maybe some material enablers and things like that. But there are the, I think there are within that context, there are a lot of implicit meanings, assumptions. They really provide the specificities of their cultural context, which we also call as heritage, right?

So the very same behavior, there's a very same tools that, in one context, and another, of course, have completely different meanings. So if we are thinking in that sense of heritages, we can put it as, I don't know if I'll put it in the right... but more or less as meaning. Right? There's

meaning, making practices of meaning, making within a certain community. Then I don't think it's enough that you look at the material aspects because on a card... so you can provide the very same behavior, the very same aspects, and then you have different meanings as obviously.

It's like saying, you know, you have the same words, but they have different meanings. So then, if you have to study, I think the, the 3D part with a project on the, on trying to elicit or make explicit even more so in some digital tool, something that, you know, the heritage that is in a recipe, it's not just finding precise in the enables, but is finding also the meanings.

And I think for finding meanings, it's a completely different game and it's very complicated. A different and to some extent, as you know, you, It's like a lost bet, like where are you going to? It's not like you have an answer. Because besides it, because that's the meaning of a living culture, right? It's something that is always related, is always, sorry, I already am going too long.

st: No, you didn't go long at all. Uh, I suppose, then I kind of want to ask, if you think that there is something potentially contradictory in the effort of capturing the intangible.

IF2301: Um, I don't know that it's contradictory. I think, I mean, if we have to really get maybe philosophical here, it is like we are condemned as humans to chase things that are ideal or impossible, right? But it doesn't mean that we don't want to chase them or we don't. It's like a, it's not...nobody can define, I don't know, love or beauty, you know? But, but it doesn't mean that you don't try to find it, right? You can define. And so I think the same here. So there are a lot of things—perhaps it happens, I don't know, if with everything that we value—but with a lot of the things that we have. Sure, it happens that, um, we, precisely because we value them, we have to somehow... I don't think we have to use the word define them, but we have to somehow characterise them. We have to say where they are, what in a sense, we have to point at them somehow.

st: Yeah.

IF2301: In a museum, you know, so if we see someone that is violating them, that is trying precisely to destroy them, so it destroys the culture. I think those things exist. You can try to destroy a culture. We have seen it in current.... You know, we're in an unfortunate political...we see it even in strategies. And we still see it, right?

So there is that, and when you see that, you think, okay, no, you shouldn't do that, or we want to precisely value those aspects, right? *Those* capture an aspect, those specifics. But then when you have to point at them, you're precisely facing that, but it doesn't mean, to me it doesn't mean that it doesn't exist or that it is contradictory to say, I value this. even though I don't know exactly how to define it. In the same way that I would say I value this person or my love for this person, even though I don't know exactly how to define. Why should I... why do I need to know how to define it, say? That perhaps it's, for me it's, I don't know if, again, maybe unless I do, it might not be appear, but perhaps as a position, but I said, I don't see it as contradictory. It's, um, it's quite interesting.

st: I'm going to regret working through ideas with you now because I'm going to then have to transcribe them and it's going to make me cringe hearing myself. work through ideas.

IF2301: [laughter] I understand.

st: Um, when I spoke to [redacted], he spoke a lot about Walter Benjamin, which of course makes sense—that is his current jam. And about the...

IF2301: Yeah,

st: And about *Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction*, basically. But in that he brought it up, it made me think of Benjamin's other work, about *The Storyteller* and the traces of the potter's fingertips on the clay and how the clay vessel is not the act of making the pot, but the clay vessel indicates the making of the pot. And then I thought, okay, this is going to be a way of thinking about the intangible.

And then when I spoke to [redacted], she talked about how seeing certain clues...well, she didn't use the word clues though I'm about to...takes us back to indicate something about the moment. And then, of course, I'm thinking about Ginsburg and his work on clues.

But now that you say this thing of... being unable to define the thing does not mean that there is no... thing itself: the problem is in the capacity to define it in a sort of contained way and the hollowness at the centre of all language or terminology or whatever. I wonder, I wonder if—I'm going to make the consortium hate me—though perhaps they already do— if I encourage us to think maybe about deconstructionism and the sort of the *gap*, like this *différance* gap between the meaning and what can be contained within a meaning and the ultimate hollowness of definitions. I don't know. It's interesting.

IF2301: Yeah, you've given me a lot to think about. It could certainly be, in this context, and I do see that as a, I don't know if it's deconstructionism, its a theory, which I, you know, which I have some familiarity, but really relative. But definitely I see that. I mean, I see the value of an approach of that sort, which, in some cases, when you are trying precisely to think of the, over the cultural value, to think of it in terms of maybe the absence, and in terms of how these absence perhaps cannot be fully expressed, and the fact that, in a way, you are condemned to try to express it.

But the game of expressing it is not, I don't, you don't have to think of it as a finite game. It's a never ending game. And you can actually, and it's a context or game. So it depends on which context, you know, you are. That is, I think that that's, you can think of deconstructionism, you can think of theories of meaning, as we know from Wittgenstein, but also why it was...but it's just the impossibility of, maybe, of covering the plane.

But the key for me is theoretically, perhaps because I'm not interested in, then, really, if you have even more so like an information system, if you have to enter into a system, okay, some youu give, so to speak, positive entries, you know? So you give precisely the finger, the fingerprints, or some other places. Or you give the tools, as I was saying, you can even give

behaviors. You can study how I'm moving my eyes now. But can any of those then define in that sense the intangible and I think, no.

And so there is a, there is a part of the gap, which, what it means is that it's not that those traces, we can use those traces, in part, the game of heritage is the game of studying those traces. But there is another part where perhaps those traces are not the heritage at all. Yeah. You could have exactly the same things, and it has completely different heritages. So what that could suggest is that you have to pay attention, because in some cases, there is something completely different from that, right? And so this is, we see this so much with media and imitation. So you think you are doing something because you are reusing precisely, maybe the tools is not...you can have reenactment, you can have mocking, you can have whatever. I don't know. In any case, it's, as we know, there is much more knowing. And so, um, Yeah, I think, depending on the situation, we might be talking about heritage, in the modern thing, or, you know, where we're moving in the gap, rather than in the traces.

st: Yeah. Would you like to elaborate a little bit on gastrospaces and how that's fitting into this notion of intangibility? On intangible cultural heritage or practice, yadda, yadda, yadda.

IF2301: Yeah, when we were working on gastrospaces, we didn't... I don't know if we didn't start from heritage, but what, in a way, where we started from, is from the fact that, you know, during the pandemic, we saw government also here in Italy, make decisions about behaviors when you had to do, you know, how you had to drink *caffè*, the bar, that where, um, made in total disregard of precisely practices.

So, I'm not saying that, you know, preserving a practice more important than preserving a life. Of course, you can just treat your...nobody would say that. But if you could preserve the lives, more or less, with the same percentages, right? Taking the same risks, but also at the same time, preserve with the heritage, and then the heritage is too reductive, you know, preserve the gastrospace, as much as possible, then you should do that. And there was no effort in doing that. There was no value placed on that. Okay.

So that was disturbing us because we thought that it wasn't just a matter of heritage, it was more a matter of if you want politics, in a very broad sense, there was a stake, right? So because it was about social engagement, social participation, education. So you had a lot of people that missed out for probably like two years or extending periods. The possibility of being exposed to socialising through certain spaces, right? Formally, meaning, making reservation, your favorite restaurant, eating, lots of informally, like in a park. Now you're playing out, you know, whatever, on a beach, you know, on a corner of the street. And if you want to sit down on, you know, in a circle and, and so this, that was the issue that we were trying to address, and we saw that for addressing that precisely you couldn't discuss the topic just based on public venues and let's say commercial spaces, or even recognised gathering spaces—officially recognised. It could also be, I don't know, a church or, you know, the club before. So it doesn't have to be necessarily commercial, it could have to be a place where it's religious or, um, but precisely some of those spaces, plus a lot of the other public spaces in Milan, if you go to a park, right, to Parco

Castello, Montanelli, whatever, it's a nice day, there's so many people socialising, having lunch breaks, plans, all sorts of stuff, right? A lot of very— intersection.

And so we wanted to have a way to discuss the political relevance of those spaces. So to speak, transversely, right? So not based on the restaurant, the pub, the cafe, which has been done in part, and there are a lot of very nice studies. But also more thinking about all of the, trying to have a tool, they could look at the... so a lens, they could look at, maybe the idea of socialising, you don't have to go and study to a restaurant, or a pub. You can go somewhere else. Perhaps we all know, but maybe we're not reminded of that. And so trying to think of how in the, you know, what is this relevance?

And then in the study, for example, in the book, what we do is that when we provide after a characterisation of what these gastrospace is, it could be, you know, the fact that, okay, it's a space, there are so many different kinds of spaces, and so, why the gastrospace? You know, I'm thinking of the importance of food and place, you know, that relationship.

st: Yeah.

IF2301: And now we'll view all of the other, maybe, many of the other disciplinary approaches to the study of food and space, put consumption in space. Terms, you know, that one could use for trying to characterise precisely the spaces where we eat. You can also, one, I think one very powerful lens is precisely, which we discussed are just starting from the tools or objects, for example, from, do you use a table, use a carpet, do you use the utensils, maybe you have the tray— a big tray that defines the space, whatever you have that tray of the space, it creates, like, the conditions for... so you can start from that, you can, all of these kind of things, maybe the kinds of people that are there, you have a chef, you have. But, um, and then we study the political, uh, maybe dimension. So if this political dimension, in what ways it can be deemed as relevant in a society, meaning you have a right, for example, to participate in society, through food spaces, you know, through gastrospace, which I think we do. Like, if I remove, if suddenly I forbid to someone to socialise through the gastrospace, it's a big, you know, it's a big violation, I think, of the possibility of a pattern, too, like, to interrupt.

And so then from there, it's easy to think, all the people that have different abilities, they don't have spaces, they represent their culture, their way of socialising. So this, so thinking of all of the value that is missed, right, for the children, to learn how their parents or grandparents would eat. For the person that cannot go to dine with their friends because kind of it, cannot enter, cannot... so all of these things.

And then type, we also have characterisation of those spaces that is very general to make studies that are really transverse between different types of places, from formal to informal. And we think of the tool in being, you know, the approach being, let's say, used from three different kinds of of people in the sense they, what we call the *gastrospace*s. So you can see yourself as a gastrospace person that you define your agency to the spaces where you eat. So, for example, if you are at home and you're invited to them or by yourself, you can actually display, you are good to yourself, or you want to cook something that connects to your mother,

your uncle, or whatever. And then uh, uh, maybe if you can go to a park and all of these things, like you become Milanese because you go to to a cafe, and have *aperitivo*. And so you perform your... and it's through those spaces. So as a gastrospacer, you can enable or not, you know, be disabled, maybe, you know, who you want to be politically, broad sense.

But then also we think about what we call the gastrokeepers, which are people that manage the spaces in different ways. You can manage a park, a beach, a street, because you are cleaning it, or you are policing people, or, but also, of course, a cafe. And so if you want to be more or less inclusive, more or less adventurous, me more or less Milanese, you can think, have different strategies of how you can do that, I don't know, *how to perform*.

So, and then a third one is what we call the gastroplanners, which are people that make maybe policies, or people that do design spaces in various ways, from, you know, you can design a, or not centre, or you may design a very specific space. But how what kind of principles you can follow? I think in my impression is that a lot of cases, maybe some gastrospac approach has been used. Again, more perhaps, to oppress countries.

So if you need to oppress the culture in different places, you really try to shut down all informal occasions for the, you know, for gathering, for... So it has been as a tool of planning more for suppression, maybe than... but sometimes, sometimes, in modern life, and let's say, places, areas, there is more, let's say, organic thing about the gastrospaces in that sense. So a lot of the thinking we're doing lately, also with [redacted], [redacted], [redacted], or [redacted], and other people in the gastrospaces— is precisely linking the theory to maybe spaces of, you know, also how you can have different heritages. Maybe if you want a different communities living together.

st: Yeah.

IF2301: Yeah, from Milan and you have, you know, these phenomena, gentrification places, so they have to live with the soup kitchen, and we have to live with their people that force me to eat *camino* on the street because there are street workers. And so how all of these, how a municipality can actually really come out all of these, together, or without having forms of suppression and without, you know, being pissing too much off—you're not gonna write 'pissing off' this is too offensive?

st: If you want, I will redact that.

IF2301: Also, I mean, these stations, right? In the sense of the fact that if people are investing in the centre of Milan for the cafe, you want to make a nice cafe, it's true. I need to be able to eat the *panino* on the sidewalk. Maybe at some point, you can just create a space where I don't have to pay.

The university is a good starting point, in the sense. I often use it also, like, in the courses. So inside the university, you can't eat, you can't bring your own food, right? And when you go to the dining hall, remember also, you can't bring your own food.

st: Really?

IF2301: Yeah, they police you. Really, like, if you sit down and you start with, I buy the food, you buy the food, and, you know, another person doesn't buy the food, they start eating it, they come, and they say, you can't eat that, or not. People are like sneaking the things, maybe, out of their box... You can't. And you can't eat anywhere else.

st: Yeah.

IF2301: And you can't sit outside to eat. So, basically, it's very difficult to bring food from home. You can go...if it's not raining, but if it's raining, what do you? That is, you know, at least there could be a couple of collegial areas, for example, where people can share their own food. Why do I need to buy? I don't have to buy it. Why, why do we, why everybody has, why? Many are relaxed about buying, but you don't have to buy. So this is, that's it. I think is such an issue. I, we talked about, I talked about this also with the, the, the, the, the government, and they don't care.

So these very basic examples... also for students, because students are very insecure. It's a moment people, I mean, some people actually work on these studies, but students are the most food insecure because the moment where you don't care about what you eat because you're young, so you think, you have a long life. And you're healthy, so you sacrifice the food to precisely for other things, and for socialising in different forms. But instead it ends up to be very important because a lot of people suffer from that. And then they do have health consequences afterwards. You know, precisely because of that, from, I mean, all sorts of kinds of health, you can think physical mental.

st: Yeah, no, it's funny. It's easier to smoke on campus than it is to eat on campus.

IF2301: [Laughter] Precisely that, precisely that.

st: Interesting. Um, there is a, there is a bar, I suppose you could call it, near my place that was built with a lot of, uh, it was a team of social researchers hired by the municipality. They wanted to build something that responded to the community, blah, blah, blah. And it's on the verge of going out of business because it *doesn't* respond to the community that's here, it responds to the community they want to have: I live in a majority Muslim neighborhood and it's a wine bar. I mean... uh, and then the other largest demographic in my neighborhood is Peruvians who, if anyone did any kind of, even cursory research, the preference for beverage there is for beer and again, they've put up a wine bar, it's this sort of bougie wine bar. It's a way of saying *you don't need to come here, this is for the young professionals, the up and coming*. But this bar isn't going to change the neighborhood... So, yeah, how it using food to not only, um, respond to existing social behaviors, but to try to preemptively engineer, who is going to be there? It's kind of interesting.

IF2301: No, really interesting stuff. Yeah, so that's the gastrokeeper. What is the... the gastroheper there? So, maybe in guidelines for gastrokeepers, you should say *don't do that*.

st: Yeah, *What are you thinking, you guys?*

Um, All right, and actually, no, another thought, uh, as you mentioned, churches as a possible gastrospace, and it made me wonder if the taking of the Eucharist is that a gastronomic act or not? Because then it stops being a— it depends on whether you have faith or not, because if you have faith, it's not a gastronomic act; it's a miracle act of transmutation. If you are not religious or not of that religion, it's an eating act. So you've got contestable gastrospace or quasi-gastrospace or ambivalent gastrospace.

IF2301: Yeah, no, no, you do. We talk about it. Also, you could have different agents because we think that the agents are a gastrospace, of course, they're not only the, not the humans. It could be that they are the humans and the ants, the rats...

st: Pigeons!

IF2301: The pigeons. Yes. So you are, I mean, if you think about it basically, that pigeons have become so integrated with gastrospace in Italy, in many parts of Italy. And they, even though people might not like it, but you know, they might not like also there's some other clients are there. And so when also the pigeons are there they don't, perhaps they don't pay, but in some cases again, they contribute to the charm or to the sight of the places. They're just agents within the gastrospace. So when you do the planning, you kind of should plan for pigeons.

st: Yes.

IF2301: In a sense, that's the point. You have to plan with pigeons.

But also we talk about... even you can you can have even components that could be the wind or the sound. Or, you know, the smoke from the cars, you know? But these are perhaps they could be some, in some cases, they can be seen as agents, because in certain circumstances, they become perhaps even more than features to become context.

For example, if you are eating in a place where your're in a landscape that you are looking at, or you are under the water, I don't know. It seems that, uh, they almost becomes really, uh, important, it's not, it's the space. And you could see some of those things as in many cultures. They do use, uh, actors, you know, they are actually things, but too.

st: Yeah. Yeah, yeah, for sure.

IF2301: So you have, so if a very fun exercise, sometimes I do words with the students, is that I say, okay, go through your house, and then if you have any part of your house, that is not a gastrospace.

st: Yeah; the bathroom.

IF2301: For you. For some...

st: Oh, gosh.

IF2301: For some people, for my mother the living room was not a gastrospace. Okay. But even the bed, or the bedroom, should never eat in bed. Some people, of course, eat in it, drink in it... but in, for example, for me, one of the kind of optimistic features of most of US cultures is that anything can be a gastrospace. In the house, anything at any time.

st: Yeah. No, it's a good a good point. The one and only time I have— very shamefully, drunkenly— eaten in the bathroom was in the United States. So it's true.

IF2301: [laughter] In the United States, everyone, every room of the house is a gastrospace. No, of course, of course. But you put basically a sign to each user, like, each gastrospace at the areas that they consider, and how these changes based on who they are with, what they're doing. That's already, it's almost a heritage exercise, right? Because it defines a lot of the heritage, for example, I think the not of heritage, even it is, is, that's the heritage of the 1st kind, right, through the, the space is the neighborhood, but using, no, you don't need, in on the bed? No. So you have your kid and you're like, no, don't eat on the bed. Get out of there.

st: My last question for you is more a practical question than anything else. As we continue in this larger project, these various concerns that we have about what intangibility is or isn't, and also knowing that we're rendering this into a digital tool... are there specific aspects of that transformation from the intangible into the codifiable that you would like to see avoided?

Like *we must, we must avoid this particular potential pitfall of...* For example. I know for me, for example, I do not want to see, I want the fact that what is made codified only hints at the intangible rather than wholly encompassing the intangible. I want that always to be foregrounded. For me.

Are there concerns like that for you?

IF2301: Yeah, so, and so, and that would be pointing right to the gap, right? One other thing that often, I mean, could be done, is nice, is that because in the end, especially with the tool, as we are developing now, the portal is, which is relatively limiting them. So, that art, but you have, in a sense, it's where it's how the, if you're on the construction, right, of the representation, what is the flow of information?

So, in that sense, one way to say this is that the two should be interactive, meaning that it should seek out, like the person that is using it should plug in some information, like what we were talking about now, what is not a gastrospace problem.

So you could see into certain things, but you can now also suggest more interactivity. We see this even with the generative tools now, like they tend to be, and they work a bit— when they work because often they still really don't work— but even when it's working, they tend to be interactive, right? You have to be able to have some sort of conversation with this machine or the opinion of the computation.

But certainly there has to be feedback because otherwise it doesn't work, and you have to learn how to give feedback to the, not a machine. And so also here, if it's a tool, either there is the feedback, or else, yes, there is a very clear frame about where the expectations are, right?

So the fact that, yeah, maybe it is, you are hinting a heritage, but there could be, there could be...and then it's up to you.

So recipes, when they work, probably recipes, collections, they do work like that. It's very codified. It's clear, if you take, uh, Artusi, it's clear, what was there? What was Artusi trying to do? You have it there, you know that you are using it. Like, it helps you, but then you plug in, whatever you want to do, with respect to what to say. But Artusi didn't have my pots, didn't have an electric stove. They have this. So you know, how to modify. But that's the starting point. It gives you...

But with our tool, it's very clear to some extent what is the ground, which doesn't mean you know how to define, but you know where you're taking this from, and a lot of the culture references, if you create a tool that is much smaller, it doesn't have a history, it doesn't have a legacy. How do you create all of the context around it so that its use is clear and you are not trying to define a culture. This is, it's a danger, for example, for me, I see it in a lot of the UNESCO Heritage List—it has that potential defect that it seems like *this is the culture*. and boom, it's codified. And then everybody, they said, there are a lot of communities, individuals, they really don't recognise themselves in that. And so they really see that as an institutional representation, almost imposition, of what cultures are, and it's not alive, you know? So it mixes all the lively point of the culture. Yeah. which, uh, so it has, in that sense, the same problem, often the geographical indications. But there's different indications. Everybody knows that they're using them, that we use them for commercial purposes. It's on a product, they are managed by producers. And, yes, there is an international frame, a governmental frame, and, you know, whatever, but it is in the end, you are talking about products that are sold. But if you are trying to represent intangible culture heritage, it's not immediately a product that is sold, or if that's what you're trying to do, then, ah, no, that doesn't seem, it's not like if we are talking and we're talking in an Italian way or whatever way, we're selling something, we are creating a product, and that shouldn't be the case. Otherwise, our... so this is where I think the misunderstanding could be. So definitely, yeah, it shouldn't, for me, I don't want to imitate. Yeah, those two, there is the risk, yeah. Yeah.

st: Artusi is such an interesting example because what is Artusi trying to do? Arguably, he's trying to make whatever dish is on the page that you're reading, but he's also trying to create a codex that will help ground the formation of this new nation of Italy. And so when I pull out Artusi from my shelf, I have to ask myself, do I want to make— I don't know— this risotto or do I want to make a country? Because the book is doing both at the same time.

My ex's family live in Tuscany. They live close to Grosseto.

IF2301: Oh, yeah.

And there is a man up the street from their house, who always made.. *finnochetto*? Remind me, the sausage.

IF2301: Ah, *finocchiona*?

st: Thank you. And then that got, that got protected status, that got DOC status a little while ago, and now he can't make it because he doesn't make it the way it's meant, meant to be made, but when he makes it the way it's *meant* to be made, no one around him feels like it's made right because it doesn't taste like what they've had for generations.

So, yeah, no. As you were saying, this sort of stamping of this is the cultural heritage. This is the cultural heritage for whom and to what end?

IF2301: Yeah, they used, actually, I know the butchers that were used for the *Finnocchiona*, and they are, you know, cited in the thing. And it's, they are not from Maremma. No, also because it's true that it doesn't, it wasn't, so to speak, God, I mean, Maremma, it didn't originate, but who cares! mean, there is a value perhaps in claiming *fonnocchiona*, as an entity, but it's true that, you know, in that case, if you're trying to protect more the heritage, then I don't know that the geographical indication might be the best precisely because of the how the rigidity is very rigid.

So, I mean, it's often too rigid with respect to space. And transformations, you know, future transformations. We have to have more flexible... Like, there can always be the past, there is a bit out of the past, so to speak, right? That makes something slightly effective, but the community might recognise that it's a legitimate example of that product. T the geographic indication doesn't allow for this. So it's a very rigid tool. It's not, and in other cases, it's basically professional. or precisely you have these software tools that are, you know, smaller labels or signs, like Slow Food Presidium, I don't know, or something like that. That is, uh, that allows a bit for a more flexibility usually, because it's not tied to any, the food, is not the vibe, or with a very complex international regulation, defines it, so yeah, other criteria.

One thing I can say is that, look, sometimes you don't have the name, which is a loss, but you can get creative, you know, food, communication, language, so you can get creative. Maybe we name some with other. That's the only thing one could say, but it's clearly a defect, you know, like an issue that we have with a lot of products where sometimes I do think that we see that the geographical indication creates such a small number of, such a small number of producers, that then they don't have enough strength to face wider markets.

And so, actually, it could even lead to the product losing relevance, and losing, you know, stunting, this is the fact that, you know, you can't replicate it as much as it was before, because it has lost its freedom to some extent of expression. So that is, many, many things that we see, they multiplied like sushi or pizza, or pasta, or whatever, they, you know, tacos, and I know they, it's precisely because they were completely free to some extent. So everybody could use them, make them their own, and... And so then, that really, there was the freedom, uh, that allowed for the, so it has a form, but not too much.

st: Mm, mm. Thank you. I think that's all of my questions. Okay. Is there anything else you want on record?

IF2301: It's good. No, no, thank you for doing this, and I hope this is useful.

Interviewee 04

IU0107: I sort of move from, from the, the—back to the historical back to the environmental. There are, cookbooks are the act of collecting recipes and recipes are...it depends on the time period, right? And it depends on what has been done. Like, have they gone through the process of printing? Have they gone through the process of editing? Have they gone through the process of, like, the intentionality. Like, fundamentally for me—and this is where I have, sort of chafed a bit at the—[redacted]'s sort of rush to collect, to collect, to collect, and, you know, to suggest that a recipe that's been written on the back of a, you know, note card and shoved into a kitchen drawer for all of eternity is a different phenomenon to something that's a particular kind of collecting, right? That there's a very different kind of action there. Maybe a little less...you know. But that's not for me to comment.

But moreover, a recipe from 1700 is very different to a recipe from 1900, right? So, in some sense you might think of a recipe in that context as a kind of modern act—as an act of modernism. And what that involves is, is, a push, an effort at reproducibility, right? And this is what, for me, [Walter] Benjamin is hugely important in thinking about recipes, like, the modern recipe: the act of reproducibility. And it's also where, I think there is an act of resistance to [redacted]'s ellipsis, um, but I also think that's where it veers toward the environment.

Stop me if I'm throwing too much in one answer.

st: not at all, not at all. I think with my---I think what I managed to say around the food that was in my mouth at [redacted]'s meeting that I'm worried of reproducing the Needham Hypothesis—

IU0107: Which is? So that I can say similarly intelligent things

st: There is this question in the History of Science, there *was* this question in the History of Science of “why did the scientific revolution not take place in China” and there was, there are all these whiggish explanations, right? And those are loosely clumped together as the Needham Hypothesis, and it takes, uh, quite a time for the realisation to be made or to be made explicit that the scientific revolution could only take place in Europe because Science is a European concept and trying to find Science in China is trying to find *Europe* in China—that we need to respect the actor's categories, the actor's ontologies, the actor's *epistemologies*, uh, so, when we find a recipe in a culture that did not organically have the recipe concept we actually impose the recipe concept on that culture.

IU0107: Yeah, that makes total sense, I would absolutely agree with that.

st: Thank you!

IU0107: No, I think there's a lot of things where, where, if we go into the project and, you know, it's sort of like, the person who walks into a forest with a preconceived idea of what, you know, a particular kind of plant is and throws out everything else and then walks out of the forest and says 'well, there are no plants there'...

st: [laughs] It's Schliemann in Troy, we're all Schliemann in Troy walkin' around like 'yeah, no, I'm pretty sure this is where it is.

IU0107: Yeah, well exactly! So if you read back into the past and decide that a recipe is going to look in a certain way and it's going to look in a particular sort of layout, it's going to use a certain font, and it's going to be described in a certain kind of way, and it's going to have a certain kind of measurements that we can feed back into the computer and reproduce something the same every time then we simply decide that the recipe is the correct way of writing things down, um, that can produce a reproducible result. And that just *presumes* the rectitude of modernity, of the industrial ideal, um, and, and I push back against that and, and...It doesn't mean that I don't accept—and I don't know where I am on this, whether, whether we should be agreeing to a completely capacious definition of recipe. So, if, if I write down, you know, *something*...that says "adding such and such sauce to, um". Well, look at it this way. Here, I'll give you an example, [Redacted] and I ate at a restaurant at the AASF conference where they served a truly *terrible* ravioli. It was a ravioli made from...the ravioli was made from, like, a ramen dough instead of a pasta dough and it was rolled out very thick and had a glopping of romesco sauce on it and both of us agreed that it was, that it should never have been made by the cook and that it should never be made by human hands again. So, if I write down on a piece of paper, um, what I just said, is that a recipe? Right? Moreover, if I take a picture of what I cooked because *I* know that I can cook it again with some reproducibility, and the if the picture is for me so that I can remember what I cooked, is that a recipe? Or is a recipe an act of reproducibility put into text that is meant for others?

I'm actually not, um, in some sense, that latter definition is a much more useful one, because it doesn't shove all acts of culinary communication under the same term of "recipe".

st: yeah

IU0107: I'm actually um, as I'm talking, I'm much more inclined towards a more restrictive act of recipes because it leaves open the possibility of *resistance* towards the recipe; to finding other ways and other places where people communicate recipes and recognise that there was a certain push at a certain time in a certain place, using kinds of technologies of printing—for example—to, um, to...communicate *how* to produce food or to *reproduce* food, and in some sense I think that is a really important distinction: to *produce* food or *reproduce* food, and it's in that that we might find the very modernity of recipe and its, and, and by allowing there to be other forms of culinary communication we can find alternatives to the things that are, that are didactic, that are modern, that are industrialised, that are capitalist, and all those other things that are about the recipe. And we can find places, even within this project for other kinds of

communications, right? And, so, maybe what I'm arguing myself into, um, is to accept and push forward with a, with, um, with a definition of the cookbook—sorry, with the recipe that, that actually accepts its relationship to the cookbook. That um, that sees a specific thing with specific kinds of power relations built in.

st: Yep

IU0107: Right?

st: Yeah

IU0107: Rather than, and that, that allows us to see not the *commonality* with the scrap of paper that I've shoved into the desk drawer, um, but rather the, um, um, the *tensions* with that piece of paper. So, I'm changing the tune entirely over the course of a single answer.

st: Well, you're allowed to.

IU0107: I'm an historian, no one cares anyway [laugh]

st: *Someone's* going to ask to see receipts!

IU0107: But with, that, but if we see Benjamin as a useful element in that, kind of, aesthetic capital value in reproducibility, that demands certain kinds of sources, certain kinds of communication, certain kinds of technology, certain kinds of, of, um, capital oriented systems of distribution and so on and so forth, and, as I was saying, that's a kind of environmental act to play with, with certain kinds of things. So...um, stop me if you want to move on, but something that I've been interested in, and [redacted] and I have been kind of talking about this, and I think it's sort of what we're going to be focussing on in Pollenzo in our presentation is, is, the, that recipes are, I think about recipes as similar, I think there's an analogy between recipes and railroad time. Let me explain: like, railroad time was that 19th century thing that recognised that the patterns of the day don't work for capitalism, right? It formed an alternative, right? So that three o'clock in New York is the same thing as three o'clock in, in, um...

st: LA?

IU0107: Toronto. Because, because trains need to run on a certain speed and schedule but that simply escapes the sun. So, it reorients people's, people's whole conception of what time is towards the needs of the train, right? And that becomes ever more urgent as you create things like telegraphs and so on, and the idea that you can send the telegram and it can go from 3:01 to 3:04 because it's actually closer to 3:04 in New York City than it's 3:02 in Tor—that doesn't work for telegram time. You have to reorient space and time to meet the needs of capital because capital moves at certain kinds of speed. The cookbook is something that reorients, um, food systems—sorry, the cookbook as a collection of recipes reorients um *nature* to the speed of publishing and the food system. In other words, we don't—for most of the nineteenth and into the twentieth century, do much in the way of recognising flows and times and patterns of growing in recipes. It would be a really interesting project to take, within our large sample of

date, to look at, for example, the, the, the ways in which we think about substitution—an idea that I'd like to come back to—and the idea that *you might not be able to get parsnips at certain times of the year*, and to look at where seasonality and patterns of growing come and go and flow and what cookbooks do that, and give you, in their recipes, give you different kinds of substitutions. This all is playing on the idea of the agglomeration as a, the, as the cookbook act. So, what this means is, is that publishing, the act of publishing, the *speed* of publishing, the distribution of books, again we're talking about modernism, right? Imposes a sort of speed and time on the natural world so that you can open the recipe to produce something that doesn't exist at that time that forces a demand for a flow of ingredients. I mean you could cook French beans at a time where there's no nearby French beans which creates an impetus, an energy for the flow, the mobility of French beans, right? But it also creates, imposes an act of standardisation, again which, again, all comes back to Benjamin, it all comes back to the notion—the ideal, the sensory ideal that, of reproducibility.

So take the carrot cake, and I really sort of like carrot cake

st: Same

IU0107: But, um, particularly with cream cheese frosting, but um, the carrot cake, um, has certain kinds of measurements that are relatively standardisable—as in it has a certain amount of sugar, a certain amount of this or that, but it also has, um, it also takes a carrot, which *can* be reproduced with a certain kind of, if you chop it up, you have to take a certain kind of violence to it—you chop it up so that you can then weigh the carrot, but all that—the reproducibility demands a standardisation of the carrot, right? So that all carrots taste the same, so that they're all the same colour, and that they're available year round, right? And that's a really interesting thing as we move toward the relationship between the natural world—the growing world; a kind of third nature, if you will, or second nature, depending on how you want to think about it—and the printed page of the written recipe. And that's, that is...the reproducibility of the written recipe demands a massive amount of standardisation so that all sugar tastes the same no matter where it's from, that all water tastes the same, that all tap water tastes the same, when you think about how much standardisation—starting from and continuing to weights and sizes—so that is a tremendous act of standardisation on the environment!

st: Yeah, it's biopower enacted on the carrot

IU0107: There you go. There you go. But it's, but I'm not sure—it is and it isn't. Is the notion of biopower capacious enough to understand that? To understand that act of standardisation? I don't know. I really don't know, but I want to think about that. Like, I really want to think about that, does that system of standardisation fit into biopower given that Foucault really wasn't interested in eating at all in his entire life, I'm not sure that Foucault is really the answer to that, if we're thinking about a kind of...I don't know, sensory discipline? Is that a better way of thinking about it? Is it a kind of modernist aesthetics? Is it a kind of... I don't know what the theorisation is but I think there's a tremendous amount for us to all think about. Is the reproducibility, is the *ideal* of reproducibility, of mechanical reproducibility in the recipe

something that's meant to evade the seasons, evade time, and evade the place. So, it *really* is three dimensional. It's—where are you, are you in Milan right now?

st: I am

IU0107: There you go, so if you and I chose a recipe, some nineteenth century recipe, and you rushed into your kitchen and into your market and I rushed into my market and my kitchen and we gathered in two hours, we should—if the recipe has lived up to its ideal—we should produce the same thing, right? So, your tap water, my tap water, all of these things should be identical. Which means there is fundamentally a relationship between many acts of culinary standardisation which begin with things like, like, the standardisation grading of things at the beginning of the twentieth century, the end of the nineteenth century, of the, like, grading of flour, the watering of beef, um, and, the naming of breeds of chickens, all the way up to the, um, genetically engineering of the late twentieth into the twenty first century, and its relationship, and the question is, is, are we comfortable with that in how we write recipes? And should we be thinking about how writing recipes that resist should be able to resist that, that, that standardisation. That is willing for you to go produce something and for me to go produce something that are totally different and we're ok with that. Like, we're good with that. But even the recipe that exists in the restaurant is meant to be reproducible. The restaurant is where we're most inclined to be Benjamin-esque. We want the thing that we ordered on Monday to taste the same when we order it again, you know, even if the growing seasons have changed, right? Which means that we're forced to reconsider the whole space of the restaurant in ways that I think we're more inclined to think about in the commercial space than we are in the private, domestic space of the recipe *depending on* who is cooking in that domestic space.

In summa, the reason I am turning to Benjamin and the reason I'm turning to the modernist act of reproducibility is that it locates us in modern markets and in Marx.

st: Yeah

IU0107: We haven't talked enough about Marxism in this, um, in this project.

st: No, no we haven't. And we also haven't talked enough about—

IU0107: Perhaps you should introduce it to the European Union, I'm sure they'd love you for that.

st: But we really haven't talked enough about Benjamin. I tried to bring him up a little at, um, a workshop recently. No, I think I'm with you. I think Marx and Benjamin always have relevance at the table. And sure, sure, get the Iranian to be the one to bring up Marxism with the European union, I'm not sure what kind of black site you're trying to get me sent to, but I appreciate it.

IU0107: You might not be going back to Cornell any time soon. I think they might want you back but the government don't.

But it is an interesting thing, it is interesting that—if we can just play the Benjamin game for a minute here—it does lead us into sensory studies, which I think is really, really valuable. Benjamin turns to the photograph because vision is much easier to reproduce than taste. And I think that suggests that, why, if he's somewhat pessimistic about photography and the moving image, would he be the same about recipes? I suspect that he might find that the limits of capital are more profound in the taste and olfactory realm than they are in vision, and I actually find that to be quite fascinating but it leads us to think about, like, restaurant reviews. Um. Which are, in effect, the judging of recipes, as, as, and a source that maybe we should go back and look at. Um, as, as something that is about the judging of recipes and the critique of recipes. I find that we can, we can actually, we can think about recipes as a place to think about the limits of the alienation of the senses. And actually *these* are spaces for resistance and revolution, and *not* vision, you know, which raises really interesting questions, like, why is it that the Russian Revolution turned in that brief moment to things like constructivism in, in visual arts, and really didn't do a lot of experimentation with food, and left, and why, why is it that futurism and fascism played with—they offered a lot of complaints about how Italy was cooking—

st: And growing, yeah

IU0107: —but they don't offer a lot of recipes for how they should cook. And a lot of what they *did* cook, and [redacted] would know a lot more about this than I do, that, from what I have seen, it's more about complaints than it is about recipe

st: Right, like “our foods made us soft and squashy so we need to stop eating our foods so that we can become strong,” but there is no clear recipe in that statement?

IU0107: Right, but they were proficient in offering new visual things: new art, new sculpture, um, and, and, there you go.

It would be interesting to think about recipes of resistance and what they produce. So, let me give you an example of one that I think is actually really successful, and it fits really beautiful with [redacted]'s notion, and is one that I think [redacted] would find a great deal of pleasure in, and to work through, it was so successful in my class—I don't know if you've heard of it, it's Grosvenor's *Vibration Cooking*. You'd love. Rush out and get it and you've gotta bring over to [redacted] to play with. Because it is, it actually, the first person she talks to in it is actually Sun Ra, who she was very close to. And what's so good is that she takes the ellipsis and makes it revolutionary—like *Black* revolutionary. And I gave it to my students in class, some recipes from it that I really just, just, ten minutes before class I said “you cook this and you cook that” and, and, they couldn't do it. And they felt really quite powerless, and they felt something about a kind of, um, outsider experience to a kind of Black culinary knowledge, and they didn't think they were colonising that Black knowledge or taking it into their own cultural expression, like, say Eric Clapton does to blues or, you know, Benny Goodman did to jazz. They were, they felt a kind of sensory power version that was really very powerful. A cookbook is not reproducible unless you get to be a part of it. In other words, there is no desire in the cookbook for you to produce what Grosvenor is interested in. Because it is, it is a collection of deeply personal

recipes that existed, that happened in moments of time, that the act of the memoir, the way in which she places them, like, one of the recipes that I had them cook was the chicken dish that she cooked because she happened to be in Harlem the day Fidel Castro came to Harlem. So she calls it something like “Castro’s Chicken” or something like that. And it’s not reproducible because the act of memoir re-replaces it in time and space and history and emotion and suddenly it looks a lot like a Sun Ra performance: unreproducible, free flowing, um, and that kind of evocation of free jazz is kind of cool because it, because it is that kind of resistance to time discipline. And I think it is a great set of recipes because there’s not much you can do with them, right? I mean you can’t, you can, you *can* cook with them but you come to terms—you’re forced to come to terms to recognise the moments of lack of knowledge. So it takes the ellipses and turns it into an act of resistance. And as a kind of visualisation, they’re really fun. And, like, it raises the, the question of whether our own visualisations are meant to be for things that you’re, you’re supposed to be able to do.

st: You’re really trying to ruin [redacted]’s life here.

IU0107: And yet, in its own success, it is something that no one uses any more. It is, in some sense, Duchamp’s toilet turned over.

st: You wanted to talk about substitution and I wonder if this would be—

IU0107: Yeah, so, I spend a lot of time in my own life on Myra Waldo who was this—this is just an academic gesture, I turn around and grab a book, like...

So, Myra Waldo, this is when I started thinking about, um, um, the act of substitution, trying to think about what that means because we all, when we cook from recipes, we all, we’re all forced to think about, well, the ellipsis, but we’re all forced to think about how recipes are *not* in fact terribly reproducible, right? That ideal is not, is, is really hard to achieve in the recipe. Most of us can’t reproduce the thing that it looks like on the page and that, that’s partly because not all ovens work the same, not all ingredients look the same, like, the natural world still resists capital. Not all flour really is the same. And, moreover, food mobilities are incomplete. I can open a Milanese restaurant here in Toronto and as I go down the list there’s all kinds of things that I can’t do, there’s all kind of things that I can’t—there are certain kinds of things, certain kinds of ingredients and that, and that’s, and that’s a first world set of mobility problems. What if I’m trying to make Indonesian food and I’m not trying to make them in Toronto, I’m trying to make them in, say some small town in northern Ontario—what is it going to look like? So that forced act of substitution relocates food in place. You can’t reproduce Milanesi food, you can reproduce a simulacrum of it—to bring Baudrillard into this—but you can’t reproduce it. With cuisine, with reading a recipe for the place where you *must* substitute is where we actually might be able to find geography. But that was what Myra Waldo was trying to eradicate. The ultimate in mobile foods. Which is, of course what [redacted] and I wrote about in our book.

So, she was the most prolific cookbook author in the United States between the 1950s and 1980s and she also wrote some of the very first Chinese, Indian cookbooks, and collected in her own mind—like, in herself—this *huge* amount of culinary knowledge that she wrote *this*—

the *International Encyclopaedia of Cooking* in, in 1967, um, it's to this day, the most incredible collection of culinary knowledge I've ever seen—it's so vast. So the first, the first, um, um, the first volume of it, the first volume—it's a two volume set—the first is recipes. The second is a glossary. So, you know, you have on the same page, something for um—a particular kind of sturgeon fish found in the pacific, a kind of beans, a lactometer, um, the Malayan word for pepper, 'ladies delight,' it's just, it's just um, I've never found...But her very first cookbook was for Panam airlines and she collected recipes from Panam employees all over the world, but throughout, it wasn't that she was writing recipes, she was substituting recipes. Like, in 1950s America you couldn't get miso so what do you do? You either leave out the ingredient in its entirety or you find an alternative. And what is the alternative? Do you find a racialised alternative? As in "this is a really gross thing, you're not going to want to eat Vietnamese fish sauce so let me find a substitution that's going to work for the presumed racialised palate," is it a "this is the only thing that capital has managed to give you"?

So, she substitutes beer for miso and that's not a sensory reproduction, like that did not fall within sensory reproduction. Like if I give you a miso soup and I don't have miso and simply pour beer into it—it's not the same. And in chemical ways and other ways—so what is a substitute? Substitution is also a way in which we recognise the limits of second nature. I mean its way, I mean its right there with the ellipsis in the ontology of the recipe and not just the ontology but the performance of turning the visual into the sensory, and it is where we think about the limits but it's *not* the same as variability. There's a set of power dynamics, and a set of environmental dynamics, and class dynamics, and, I think, I think, it's a concept we really need to work through.

st: What is the distinction between the substitution and the variable? Because it struck me as you were speaking that I was being asked to think of all of the authentic Iranian cooking of my childhood as actually a culinary simulacrum because they were made, they were made—and I mean, this was a complaint of my mother's my whole life, like *this isn't the right tomato paste*, which, *sure*—the tomato paste could be wrong but this was still an authentic *ghormeh sabzi* at the end of it, so what is the—

IU0107: That's not the same substitution as, you know, like—

st: yeah, replacing coriander with—

IU0107: Give me a second, I want to find this for you, her, this is the Panam one, and this is her Iranian recipe

st: Oh, you want to see me get mad? Alright, let's go

IU0107: The, um, um, so let's see. Because I think, let's see. You're mother's substitution is one we might think of as the real, um...

st: My mother's I understand as the real against which all simulacra are forms. Her's is the authentic that can never be replicated, as far as I'm concerned. So whatever they're making in Iran is a simulacrum of what my mum makes in Cherrybrook.

IU0107: But it's also an experience of diaspora. It's an experience in which she was forced to recognise the, the, um. It's an experience in which she was forced to recognise the kind of gendered expectations of reproducing ethnicity in the domestic space. Um, and so we might think about hers as a very, a very kind, as a form of resilience, which is *hugely* different.

So she [Waldo] was, and none of this should surprise you, she was thinking of Iran in terms of the airline, and how an airline understands space. So she turns it into, um, um, Arabia, Iran, Iraq, Afghanistan.

st: Ok, so she's trying to start a geopolitical event, alright, go off, Waldo

IU0107: So she writes "they are joined together for several reasons; they are neighbours, they are Arabic speaking, and they share the same religion" *none of which are true*.

st: I mean, there are ethnic Arabs in Iran—

IU0107: Starting with countries, right? They're *not* joined together, they are *not* neighbours in any kind of sense in which we might understand that term, and they are not Arabic speaking, and on some level they're not the same religion. I mean you might say on *every* level they are not the same religion. That's a kind of airline imposition that, that, if you think about space as "we fly to Spain because we land in Madrid" no-you don't fly to Spain, you fly to Madrid. So, Panam flew to a few places, a few cities, a few airports, which she then imposes a certain kind of visualisation.

Then she offers a few terms which she puts in lower case font. So she writes "Fantastic Persia has been superseded by present day Iran but many of its former colourful former ways remain, like a colourful *FitzPatrik Traveltalk*, the streets and marketplaces are lively beyond our imagination." So she gives us a recipe for "Arabic Stuffed Peppers" in her recipes but then gives us a set of vocabulary, like, *wurrs*, which have been turned into Roman characters and doesn't consider these might be from entirely different languages from entirely different language groups. Um, so. She gives us "Roast Chicken with Sweet Stuffing" from this amorphous space imagined in this neocolonial, postcolonial, colonial geography.

So, and all of these are recipes she gives by already substitution out other recipes—because they're too gross; because they can't be cooked, so it's a set of things like a lentil soup, certain things which are, um, so she gives us certain things like, she goes "lentils. Pink if available." And then she writes "one half cup *burghal* – cracked wheat". So in the translation she's already giving us substitutions. She gives us "Farina nut dessert" and "bean casserole"

st: Ok, yeah.

IU0107: So certain kinds of, when, one, you think about the translation, the vocabulary, substitutes, “Stuffed squash casserole”, substitutes some terms for another

st: Yeah, “casserole,” *girl*.

IU0107: Exactly. It puts it directly into a 1950s home where there were plenty of casseroles. It is capital. It’s all kinds of different things. So if we think about recipes for their absences, we also have to think about them for their substitutions.

So there’s a conversation that I think needs to happen between the philosophical stuff, that, you know, you guys are doing, *and* the, the political and sensory economy of substitution. Um, and I think these are, these are really interesting things to think about.

And there is an authenticity thing about it. Like, if, at what point did it, like, for you as a child, eating it, it must have *always* been Iranian, because of your mom’s hands, because of your relationship to your mom, because of her intentionality, because you’re looking at this from the perspective of a number of years, ummm, and so on and so forth, so it was Iranian by its very—implicitly that. But at what point in your mom’s substitutions was there something that she wasn’t going to cook, simply because she couldn’t do it, or because it would have meant so much substitution that at some point it crossed a red line? And if she had cooked *these* recipes—we might think of Waldo’s recipes as acts of appropriation of violence, and I think that thinking through all the itty bitty processes of substitutions, we might come up with something more important than appropriation. Because substitution might be really, they might be acts of resistance, they might be moments of loss. But substitution can also be acts of appropriation or violence at the same time. So what do we do with this, the, what do we do with the moment of, the act of substitution? And one, sort of, final example of that is when we impose taste or diet.

So this is where the online section of recipes becomes relevant. Like “I substituted chicken for pork and it was terrible” like, of course it was fucking terrible, it’s not the same recipe any more. How many times, from different perspectives can you substitute before it ceases to be the recipe?

st: Yeah, yeah, yeah, the sushi train of Theseus.

IU0107: So, at some point there’s a relationship between language substitution and ingredient substitution, which is an engagement between food mobility systems, between structures and, um, sensory responses. So you may substitute out the lovely little cutlets of lamb for the lamb head because you don’t want to eat the lamb head because it’s *gross*. Do you see where I’m going with this?

st: yeah, I’m... I wonder if you’ve thought about the substitution of...the ways we feed ourselves can also be tied into larger cosmologies. I’m thinking about how Indonesian *Jammu* is, in some moments, from the analyst view, a culinary method and in others a pharmaceutical practice, but in actor view, it’s both. Or, how in Iranian cooking you need to balance your hot and cold elements because if your food isn’t balanced you’ll presumably fall ill or what have you, so we

think carefully about our ‘balancing ingredients’ but now, in this ostensibly modern, connected, western hegemonic world, we might learn that our balancing ingredient gives you, I don’t know, leads to high cholesterol or something, and then the Western fact of cholesterol is given precedence over the hot cold balance of the universe because of that Western hegemony and cultural supremacy.

But then, sorry, lastly, if I “resist” by choosing to eat my cholesterol spiking food and telling myself “I’m going to eat this even if it raises my cholesterol,” my paradigm is already shifted, because it’s not unhealthy in the original paradigm, I’m now eating *in spite of*.

IU0107: I agree, I think this is part of the larger universe of substitution that I need to think about. And, and also gets at the very tensions of recipes as forms of communication across time and space. And the limits of reproducibility.

So there’s another element of this that I want to flag, because it’s something that we can do with big data. And it’s something that, this is, um, this is where substitution reaches its limits in interesting ways.

So if we go back to her recipe for squash casserole, which she calls, um, *mas bahat et dawish*—to take her translations, or basically, putting it all into Roman characters, there is multiple, if I just give you the ingredients, can I?

st: Please

IU0107: And you can just check off all kinds of one to one substitutions. So, “two pounds zucchini or yellow squash, two teaspoons salt, one cup American or cheddar cheese—”

st: Haram. Ok.

IU0107: “One half cup cottage cheese, four eggs, something too small for my eyes to see, breadcrumbs, parsley, pepper, butter.” It’s *clearly* a casserole. What continues to ground it as something foreign in the domestic sense is the use of a set of words that are, even to my own ears, unpronounceable. So It’s um, you can cook this and it feels very, very foreign in a domestic sense to *you* but do we know where it’s from? It doesn’t matter where it *is*, but that it’s come *from* some place. But then we can think about her Arabic lentil soup, which she called “shorabat adaas”.

St: [laughter] That one is closer!

IU0107: Right. But she reaches the limits of her substitution with the cracked wheat. Because she leaves the word burghul but she leaves it in Italics. And, have you read, we had a round table a few years ago in Gastronomica on, on um, italicising words.

St: I didn’t

IU0107: I would love to hear your response to the round table because we decided we were not going to italicise ingredient words anymore and that this is a, a stylistic choice that we were going to impose upon writers. Because certain words were not being italicised. Like sushi was not being italicised anymore but, say, kacha paani *was*.

St: Right, when is it a naturalised citizen of the culinary world...

IU0107: Exactly. So we decided we were no longer going to accept italicisations, and um, and we had a long, sort of, round table that we just sort of taped and just decided to, to print the whole round table. So there was this really interesting question for us in the, the process of print. Because if we think about recipes as *printed*, as having gone through the action of being typeset and printed, then we need to think about what italicisation is—the use of things that cross language, ok? And so, and this is part of why I think I am encouraging us to think about the distinctions, that we should use the same word for the printed recipe and the recipe handwritten and passed down, or handwritten and not passed down and, you know, and we should also think about things like marginalia, um, but, we should think about italicisation. If she prints burghul and then puts in italicisation “cracked wheat”, which you and I know is not in 1950 the same thing, um, is it because it’s untranslatable? Is it because it—and therefore substitutable? Is it because she’s looking to create a kind of authenticity? Is it ‘cause she’s presuming that many of her readers might have actually had access to that kind of ingredient in many of the stores and spaces, that the food mobilities had caught up to the recipe itself? Is it because she’s trying to give the recipe a sense of authenticity, right? So what do we do with that?

By the way, you’ll be keen to know that Fattoush she translates as...one second

st: Is it “salad Shirazi”? Because that’s what the closest analogue would be called in Iran

IU0107: No. “Mixed salad”

St: Mixed salad! Well I guess it’s not, you know, kept in separate lumps.

IU0107: So there’s a whole lot of substitutions, there’s tomatoes, cucumbers, mixed peppers, scallions—

St: wait, she’s putting green peppers in it?

IU0107: Why not? Bread crumbs, olive oil—sorry, bread *cubes*, lemon juice, olive oil, salt and pepper. Many of her readers would have been able to get many of those things and it *is*, in fact, a mixed salad. And its Fattoush only because she calls it that. And there’s nothing italicised in it. So we could do a lot with a big data set when it comes to italicisation. So we could, for example, feed huge amounts of data—presumably—and see when certain ingredients cease to be italicised. And you, and you could graph it. Like, sushi, none of us would italicise that. But when does it cease? And does it ever pick up again?

And to take the case of Iran, as Iran goes from being “friendly” in 1954, to um, um, *enemy foreign* in 1984, to pick a random, post-revolutionary date, um, you see what I’m saying?

st: You mean, like, how we started calling orcas “killer whales” again when they started sinking yachts. The same kind of rhetorical trick?

IU0107: Yes, so I just want to flag the many kinds of things that fall into substitution as something to think about in our work moving forward but we also *really* need to think about italics.

St: No, these are really good matters to flag, thank you. Really interesting.

I think the concern I have, if I think about... I don’t know, maybe this speaks to a particular character flaw of mine—I don’t have an image in mind of what I want this project to look like but I certainly have a lot of ideas in my head of what I *don’t* want it to look like and what I’m afraid it will look like.

IU0107: I would second and third that feeling. And I guess I would say, and I guess I’ll pass you this question; I’m so afraid, I don’t know that I want it to look like anything *at all*.

St: Yeah? I hear you. I wanted it to look like a postdoc, man. That’s all I wanted it to look like.

IU0107: [Laughter]. So [redacted] was forced to be practical because he’s a librarian, and I’m a theoretician; so I can deal with things that are not, that are not meant to be possible. So, he raised the possibility that you could take recipes, and you could colour code them in certain kinds of ways.

st: yeah, I was thinking the other day that even this taxonomy of “is it a soup? Is it a starter? Is it a salad? Is it a main?”—I can’t stand it. People come over to mine for dinner and they anticipate dessert and we don’t have that concept. Like, I gave you fruit before dinner, what do you want a sweet for? But in relation to what you said about [redacted] and colour, my thought was about wetness. Like, “is it a wet meal? Is it a dry meal?” Can we just put this on a hydration scale?

IU0107: But you could also imagine something, you could imagine the ways in which, we could take a recipe, you and I could work on a recipe together and we could flag in, like, links, things where we’ve opened up discussion where we talk about certain ingredients, why we’ve chosen this ingredient over that ingredient, you could select an ingredient and see how its own composition has changed over time. But you could also geolocate, you could locate an ingredient so as to try and resist as we move from the printed page which is implicitly non seasonal, as we move into the digital you could do recipes that, um, change colour

St: yeah, Eurasia getting redder as Columbus introduces tomatoes

IU0107: Because there are recipes that you can make in Toronto—Iranian recipes you can make in Toronto—that you can make in Toronto but you can’t make in Timmins because you can get the ingredients in Toronto but not in Timmins so the recipe is not *possible* in Timmins. So

certain ingredients as you geolocate it move from green to yellow to red—so it holds onto the recipe as something representable but not reproducible that I’m hoping we can use when it comes to our visualisation. Recognising that visualisation does not mean taste. Does that make sense? I’m not sure it makes sense to me. But the recipe might be something you can study, you can look at it, but you shouldn’t cook it.

St: right, like your awful ravioli. And you could make the argument that it ought be written down in order to prevent anyone from ever thinking to make this again, like a cautionary recipe that’s not intended for cooking. Or, I guess *The Anarchist’s Cookbook* is a cookbook but not one you should be making things out of.

IU0107: Or *Vibration Recipes* which are good to look at but which you shouldn’t be cooking because you can’t move from the olfactory to the gustatory. And this leads us to thinking, can we call out people’s privilege? There is very little in my recipe bank that I think “this cannot or should not be made by other people,” which isn’t to say I’ve so lost my roots that they cannot be redressed, but that I’ve simply claimed everyone else’s roots. That I’ve become the omnivore by simply, simply by being white.

st: “Max Bellyroom”

IU0107: There you go. It isn’t the omnivore’s dilemma, it’s the omnivore’s privilege. Everyone’s food is mine because of white privilege. But we can use the visualisation exercise to put back into the work time and place, and to undo the violence that is all Gutenberg’s fault.

St: Right. And it would allow us to bring in Benedict Anderson who I think is really both crucial to and absent in this project of containing and capturing European identity as this simultaneously open and closed thing. This us and Other thing.

IU0107: I’m sure Anderson would have many good things to say about italics

St: I’m sure it would be a Verso bestseller.

IU0107: But there’s maybe something to being content with the limits. Like we shouldn’t be just enabling Europe to open its doors to everybody who wants to consume it, right? We should have words that are just “sorry you can’t translate this, this is too located, this is not a mobile ingredient, tough shit” Or the recipe you should not make because you’re not entitled to it. Yeah, I mean, I think we need to be really careful when with think about the big data set.

So, anyway, those are the things that I’m just sort of really, really interested in, and things that are on my mind, And I’m really trying to work through many, many different elements of substitution. I’m also trying to work through recipes as, I mean, I’ve thought about a lot of, you know recipes in terms of mechanical reproduction and now I’m trying to think of recipes as, as environmental acts.

St: I think that might be—I’ve taken a lot of your time

IU0107: Yeah, let's—the sun is...my child is still asleep, my cat is just waking, so...I'll see you in Pollenzo, right?

St: I think so, Insha'allah.

IU0107: Excellent, excellent. I will see you there. Ok, talk to you soon

st: yep, ok, ciao ciao.

Interviewee 05

st: Thank you, first, for meeting with me separately, I know you've not got much time, I don't, um, I don't want to take too much more of your time.

IW0407: It's no problem, I can, I have a bit.

st: So, um, I'll get back to the last point we got to in the group—this, um, ok, so we talked a fair bit about recipes and intangibility only, it didn't, we kind of got to it at the end, but I'd like to work through that a bit more. So, I guess, my question is, when we engage with the intangible, I mean, we're trying to make a framework for engaging with the intangible, right? Engaging with this thing that is, kind of defined by its, by, uh, for being uncodifiable—though now we're making it codifiable for a platform. Gosh, [laughter] I'm still not asking my question. Basically: What do you understand intangible cultural heritage to be and what, um, what do you see as possible hazards?

IW0407: Mm, yes, I want to answer in a, maybe, in a bit of a mix way, because for me the questions of preserving and creating are not so...they are not separate.

So, when I think intangibility, first thing, um, first thing for me is, is, is that it's not really, we don't actually want to say it's intangible, no? I mean, we talk about intangibility and we want intangibility and then we show tangible things, we take measures, we make picture, we want to put it in a database, to make a platform.

So I get a bit suspicious when we talk about the intangible as something that just floats, as if we can catch it and then put it somewhere more safely, um, because usually, usually, or really, what is called intangible is precisely what can't put in a database.

st: Yeah, this is, um, yes, this is a problem, I agree.

IW0407: And recipes are a good example because it is not, um, in a way it is nothing; the recipe does not mean a taste, or show you when you should eat it, or who you should, you know? It is just, it is a record that, um, it is a record that maybe does not even record anything real. Or, or it is a reminder. And then you make the recipe but you, you don't actually make the recipe because that's not how you cook. You always have to change because your kitchen is

different—my kitchen here is different to my kitchen at home which is, is different, you know, to my kitchen where I first learned, or the season is different, the time is different, my age is different, or you can't get this ingredient or, or, you don't eat it in the right company: I want to eat it with this person but I can't so I eat it with this other person and this is not the same thing, you know?

So already there is contradictions, you want to, to, and of course, writing down a recipe is not wrong, and sometimes it is good, sometimes even maybe it is political, but we should not pretend it's really this thing in the world.

st: Right.

IW0407: Also, I will be honest, maybe this is more personal, but when I hear this language of protection – protecting heritage, what is our word in RELISH? Reserving?

st: Reimagining, I think? Though I always mix it up in my head and think its 'Recapturing' which is maybe telling [laughter]. Perhaps a bit, um, telling of my, my worries.

IW0407: No, I do the same. Ok, Reimagining, but I think really its, um, it's, it's reclaiming, or, as, as they like in these EU language, *safeguarding*. And, like, ok, but from what? From change? From mixing? From people moving? Because change is not always loss. Sometimes it's survival. You said it was, what? Revision? Reimagine?

st: Reimagining, yeah. Or, maybe I should check...

IW0407: OK, but, OK, so, um, listen; Europe being “under threat” is not something that I am worried about. I think maybe it would be a bit good for a change, for, for Europe to experience what, what Europe did to everyone [laughter]. Where I come was colonised by Europe and now I am here and I see that the same people colonised are seen as coming and threatening, or they are changing, so, so, if anything, I think sometimes this sort of projects are racist, right?

st: Yeah, this has... I've felt a bit uncomfortable too.

IW0407: Where is Europe disappearing to in 2025 that now they, they need...Ok, so we make a platform that says 'OK, real European food is in here and now is safe'. From what? Safe from you and me, I think [laughter].

st: [Laughter]

IW0407: And we laugh but really, everything is, it is not, it doesn't celebrate *oh, look how we change, how we evolve, have evolved*, it is always more like *we are so fragile, we could be lost any time* and all this, this, hybrids, hybridity becomes corruption.

And then when recipes enter this picture, they can very easily become ways of hiding these bad things. We preserve one place's recipes and we don't say that they made this recipe because

they stole it from some other place in the world, or that these ingredients come from a land they invaded. And, and, I mean, I don't care, I am not so connected to this RELISH, but I think it is a big, it is a problem you have.

It is, you know, Europe likes cohesion, it like multiculturalism, it likes everyone together, but it doesn't really, you know? [Laughter] But you know how I mean, no? Like it talks and talks but [laughter]

st: Yeah, I think, um, no, yeah, I hear you. It's like a Benetton ad but its always abstract.

IW0407: Another contradiction, another problem sorry, I jump, is this thing about, about being old. Heritage is always old, it is always some, I don't know, its, like its eighteenth century, its, but why? And actually this is not true, not always true. And we are always reinventing. Or what does it, how can I say I am making traditional food in my modern kitchen, I can't say this is, is, you know, continuing practice. It is adaptation. And that doesn't make them less meaningful, but why can it not be that, you know, ok, we have more Syrians in this place now because of war, because of whatever, and they take the ingredients that are here and they try to make their food, why is that not heritage?

st: Yeah, yep. I like, I always think of pizza kebab

IW0407: Sorry, what do you—?

st: Oh, sorry, pizza kebab. It's, it's what it sounds like; its pizza topped with kebab.

IW0407: [Laughter] Ok

st: It's perfect when you're drunk [laughter]. But, um, like, my point about it, or, the reason I think about it is that it seems here to be both, um, like, an object of criticism, like *that is not pizza* and a kind of shorthand for, like, the people who make it or eat it. Like, the Egyptian pizza guys, the, sorry, *pizzaioli*, I think, will never be authentic. Or, um, the Moroccan teens who are always diminutive in Italian: *Marocchini*, they are never Italian. And why? Or, like, why not? Why can't, um, so, I might be wrong, I think the *vero pizza* association, I'm, whatever, sorry, I'm blanking its full name; the protectors of pizza, their protection relates to the crust. So if I make the right crust and I put kebab on top and *toum* and, you know, why, like, why not?

IW0407: Exactly, why is it not allowed to be cultural heritage, intangible culture?

st: Personally, I find it less disturbing than the, the, have you seen wurstel pizza? [laughter]

IW0407: [Laughter] Maybe because that one is inter-European.

st: [Laughter]. Ok, well, I don't want to keep you—

IW0407: No, I have to, I should

st: Right, and thank you again, really, this is really, this is really, yep. Thank you

Interviewee 06

IT0506: Okay

AB: Okay, so, um—no, let's, I think the purpose of this conversation is really to see, also, based on—it really comes at the end of a lot of work you've done, also for this, like, work, and, but also for the project. And so, look; we can start.

I'd like to see, um, you know, how you, how you view the work, but I'd like to start, actually, from the more tangible aspects. I'd like to start actually from how you, um, began studying food issues and especially the intangible aspects of food issues. You know, in the sense, in both ways, if any, you know, the intangibility that is part of this—*the heritage*—and tangibility, were part of your work. So, I don't know, these are probably two questions, right? One is how did you start to work on food? And the other is, in both ways, if any, then intangibility was part of that or not, because, I guess...we can start from the first to the second, you can ignore, you know, the first, however, if you prefer.

IT0506: Okay. This feels like a job interview: I'm having flashbacks to... having flashbacks to December 2025.

Uh, So. My entry into studying food, I need to start a little bit before food, right? My scholarly interest has long been in systems of population production and management: so homogenising structures. And that can be at all sorts of different scales and in all sorts of different contexts, right? We can think of Foucault and Goffman here, right? You have systems of population making, turning individuals into population for the purpose of governance, at scales like in the classroom, but you also have it at the state level, so, like, big and small.

And there was this period in, probably during the pandemic where, like a lot of the world, I was terrified of being left alone with my own thoughts, so I was binge listening to a lot of podcasts, and something that I was listening to was the BBC Food Program, and the episodes, I noticed after a period of time, they really started to lean in on this idea of tradition and foods tied to particular people, and those people being tied to geographies, and the whole thing being under threat—everyone is under threat, this almost bogeyman threat. And there was one episode in particular that I remember, wherein the host, Sheila Dillon, was talking about the different fats in which one can make Christmas potatoes. And obviously, this is another way of talking about Britishness, right? And about tradition, authenticity. And she went into a rage about how if you make your Christmas potatoes in mustard seed oil, it's not going to taste like Christmas; it's going to taste like Indian food.

And I remember thinking, lady, you need to calm down because nobody is coming into your kitchen and telling you that you have to change your oil to mustard seed oil. You have invented an Indian lobby that is out to ruin your Christmas, to be afraid of. Uh, and so this really got me

started on this thing of how are we using the ways in which we talk about food to actually talk about people, how are we taking the very familiar adage of *you are, what you eat* to say, *you don't eat like us so you're not one of us* or *I'm going to make you something by telling you what to eat*. So that's how I got really interested in food as a population management or production system.

But the intangible aspect of this really came in later, as I was studying more and more, these systems that regulate food, because one of the biggest schemes that we have for protecting and preserving—and cynic that I am, I hear protecting and preserving, and I hear something Western anxiety alarms go off of my head—is intangible cultural heritage. And the idea that you would have a registry of intangibility makes no sense because intangibility is not registerable. Like that is the, it's, it's almost like a codification of tacit knowledge: that makes no sense.

So the two kind emerged together. I hope I've answered the question, have I? I don't think I have.

AB: Yes. In a way, you know, actually moving it slightly, so—a lot, when I hear a lot of speech, right, there is no...it says you talk about population, like, control management. But then it is, there is also some idea of, sometimes it could be fabrication, that we will know that is a publication of tradition. But... I think there are different elements here, you know, that we could talk about.

So, one is the, um, uh, let's say the action of producing, uh, um, in an record of the intangibility aspects of the traditional aspects. What can you tell me more about that? Because their action is not necessarily always intentional, and then, as we know, intentions can't always line up with results—with the outcomes. So that's where I also think it becomes, I don't know, can become interesting. So I'm just trying to think here, how much do you see the outcome of the fabrication of tradition as the outcome of specific intention by people. And then what other parts, you know, shape, uh, uh, this mechanisms.

So this, you shape seconds narratives, but it's not necessarily that one is better at shaping them. So we have some sort of collected-without-necessary-being-connected rationality and efforts, right?

I'm just thinking—to me—to, to see if you have any particular...if you think some of them are, if some of some processes are more relevant than others, or what can you tell me more? Something about that?

IT0205: Um, I don't think that I—

AB: —The question is—

IT0506: —Oh, I'm sorry, go ahead

AB: The question is fluent, but I don't know if it's clear.

IT0506: I don't know if it's clear, but I know that my answer won't be either, so at on that we're equal.

Um, I'm not sure if this is the question exactly but I don't think, I don't think of there being any single, you know, nefarious body that does this fabricating process. And I definitely don't think it's always intentional.

There is no like secret cabal of food, standardisation people trying to control populations around the world. I'm not trying to fuel conspiracy. Though there are certainly some who are definitely using food to make populations, right? I don't think we can look at Um, Salvini's Twitter and think that he is doing anything other than using food to talk about the Italian body. And I don't think, really, we should look at what is being done by Lollobrigida as anything other than trying to use food as proxy for talking about the preservation of some sort of Italian body. But other times these things are more organic.

Um, so you know, uh, somewhat recently, within the last few years, understandably, discussions about hummus and the cultural appropriation of Palestinian food by Israeli settlers. I mean, there the food itself becomes this physical marker of a thing that is otherwise far more diffuse. How do you address almost 80 years of settler colonisation quickly? You talk about Sabra hummus, right? But Palestinians drawing attention to appropriated food is fundamentally different to, um, Salvini complaining about Turkish nuts in Nutella because there is a power imbalance here.

Oh, gosh. Um, I think I've lost the thread of the second half of your question. Could you remind me?

AB: No, so here, now you are saying multiple levels of that, because I think you are going to the structure of the, uh, or maybe trying to make some distinctions between clearly there is not one of the population, you know, like global.

Then I think maybe you were getting into, I understand, the idea that with some constructions—I call them this way, even though it's not a term that I use—with some construction, some of these, uh, you know, uses of food, they might be more...I don't know, *genuine* than others? Or certainly they seem to be less fabricated than others, something like that? Because I understand, because they respond to some general issues that are out there...but I don't know if I'm adding words here.

IT0506: No, I mean, I think by and large, it's quite genuine. If we put aside, for the moment, things like advertising, right? What happens in the world of advertising we can treat as somewhat more cynical. But in so insofar as it comes from actual literal consumers, uh, I think that there is always a genuineness to it, even if the food is only a vehicle for expressing that more genuine thing.

I think a population that feels threatened, right, or feels that it is being erased in some way or that it's being stolen from, might use food to express that bigger sense of theft, and that feeling

of theft is genuine. But the food might not be the sum of it all, more like synecdoche. The food becomes a rhetorical device in such a setting.

Uh, But it does seem to be increasingly trendy as the language with which we talk about appropriation. Um, About what was it, five, 6 years ago, time has kind of become all blurry for me. Actually, it would be closer to 10 years ago— when Jamie Oliver made jollof rice because he's Jamie Oliver, and he's a moron.

Um, but he made jollof rice...when he made this abomination of jollof rice, it became the sort of touchstone of *what is cultural appropriation? How do we discuss cultural appropriation? What is appreciation?* Which itself sidelines the fact that jollof rice is a disputed food between other nations, right? Uh, nations who can all agree that it's not a British food, so there is some sense of theft, but the way it was talked about made it a bit Britain versus monolith Other place that makes jollof and which calls us good people appropriators.

Here the example, the example happens to be food. That frustration or offence was, is really genuine, I think. Um, I think I'm doing a really bad job of answer your questions, to be honest.

AB: No, no, this is good! One thing, one other, um...no, I think I can see two other things here.

One is, in those cases, you know, because at the beginning, we were saying that um, er, there is an element of publication, right? Even in the jollof rice. But if I understand what you're saying now, is that... it can morph, however, to... it can be *possible*, however, to, to say what their fabrication is *not*.

Like, for example, the genuineness now that you are expressing some places, or the, where there is really an issue, it's in the negative, right? So it's in the negations where you see... When—so there are clear cases where you say, that's a no, right? It's much harder to see where there are places where that's a yes, where there is no fabrication, because every...every time we claim a tradition within something, maybe you could think there is always an element of selection, right? That it can be seen as a fabrication or invasion.

So here what I'm thinking is, because that happens with a number of other...other cultural items. So it's easier to tell when there is a violation that is being made, then when there is an act of, uh, when there is a claim, a positive claim, which can be recognised as not, not being somewhat constructed, fabricated, invented, whatever.

Do you think there is any, anything interesting there? Like, this is a negative plane.

IT0506: I do think there's something interesting there. I wonder if part of what makes it so difficult to find, um, a pure, genuine claim here, is that...what these things each defer to are always social constructions. So the... The jollof rice becomes a metonym for nation, but nation isn't a natural kind; it's a social kind. And at a different point in time, that nation might have been grouped differently. It might have not even been a nation. It might have been part of a much... I see this a lot, especially with foods of my region, right? This sort of, *oh, no, that's not*

Turkish food, that's Iranian and then that's not Iranian food it's Afghani, well, there was a time when we were a cohesive region.

So I think maybe part of what makes it difficult to find a sort of, *is this representation true? Is it pure?* Is that it's almost like asking, is there a...is there a natural kind to which this social kind refers to? And no, it's social all the way down. I think, with the stuff that we're talking about—

AB: Nice. So, because here, then we can see, you know, you have a mapping on to either a geographical region, or a population, but the boundaries of the geographical region, the population, are, of course, something. So it's easier to know when you're outside of the region, like, *hey, look, you are in England: this is clearly not that region*, but then if I tell you to tell me exactly what are the boundaries of the region, you'd say, *I don't know*.

I mean, it's not like, you know...know exactly how to draw those lines.

IT0506: Yeah.

AB: But I know where, more or less, you know, they're certainly not.

IT0506: Yeah. Yeah, yeah.

It's really interesting in our own project as well, right? It's this *European* food legacies thing, right? So it's at once making a claim on *what is Europe?* And it's an EU funded project but it includes the UK, which is famously no longer EU, right? But clearly the people in this project feel it's still... it's still European in vibes, right? We still recognise the UK as European in a way that I think if we were maybe, put into a quiet, protected space where we didn't have to make eye contact with one another, and we could look into our heart of hearts, we would all agree that Turkey was never going to be invited into this conversation, right? Turkey was never going to be invited into RELISH in a way that the UK was.

I mean, this project isn't just talking about European food legacies, It's also remaking, reasserting Europe. It's... it's defining Europe in the process of making legacies in Europe.

AB: But there could also be suggestion here about, uh, how to think of...what I would call now for simplicity, the 'logic of heritage', that it should work as a negative logic, not as a positive logic, because you should not think of it, as...as you say, in terms of positives. but in terms of negatives. So like, what is excluded rather than what is included? Because that could be maybe it's a better game, so to speak, to play. It's a good game, rather than the inclusion game, because the inclusion game, I mean, you can do that, but when you're doing that, you think, come on, here, you're really doing politics in a way that the some of the clear extrusions are maybe... I don't might know, I don't know, but I'm thinking...

IT0506: Yeah, so heritage work is Boundary Work to use the vocabulary of—

AB: Yes, you could think of it like that...but the thing about boundaries is that it's exclusion space, because it's not necessarily that you're demarcating a boundary. This is why... because if you say what it's not, you haven't said where the boundary is. Right?

IT0506: Okay, yeah.

AB: If I tell you... you know, is this on Mars? No, it's not on Mars. Is it on the moon? No, it's not on the moon. So if you go by exclusion, right? Is it in the middle of the Pacific Ocean? No. But then, is it also in Canada? Maybe yes. So pieces get created. So some areas are more borderline, but you might know, you might not do the... So, okay, this was one thing that I think could be relevant to for the Project One, but another was, I don't know, like, to see your opinion about the, if you think, so for now, we talked about maybe the regions and the people.

IT0506: Mm hmm.

st: And we look about it back there, also, because maybe it's not only people, it could also be kind of like the animals and living organisms. But if we go back to think about the, I wanted to think also about the foods, the dishes, the recipes, if they play an active role, or demarcation role, or not?

Like, so, you know, to do, to do demarcation with fries, or to do it with, uh, um, anything, any other product, like a whiskey or a spirit, are...are they all on a par with sugar? Is it, you know, are there some elements? Is there some aspect of the food or the dish, that, by, let's say, its own nature is more prone to serve in this role of heritage making? Right? Like what kind of aspects should the food have? And, uh, you know, uh, maybe I'll leave it there.

IT0506: Uh, within the sphere of heritage studies—within critiques of heritage work within the sphere of heritage studies—there has been a lot of discussion about how this sort of preservation work has um, a troublesomely Western, let's just say, flavour to it—I'll throw in a pun: it has a *flavour* to it.

Uh, so, a lot of this sort of turn to sustainability is itself like this, this, it's a Western value that's being imposed outside of the West. And I see recipes as doing the same thing. If, If the Western mode is this record keeping, archiving mode, and I'm just, I'm just talking like basic, um, *the Order of Things* type emergence of Western civilisation here, then this sort of drive to make the archive, to make the recipe, to record it, to recognise it as a specific form rather than a continuation of other practice. Like, uh, there might be a context in which, for example, a recipe is—what would be viewed as a recipe from this Western perspective—might be considered part of a song or part of a mode of lullaby or, mnemonic or something like that in another context, right? But to pull it out and say that this can be *recipified*. Is this, uh, it is this, um, reassertion of a form of ordering that I guess... I guess, again, is doing this exclusion work, this border... this border-making work.

So for me, the question of can sugar be a recipe? Can sugar be a recipe that is equivalent in recipe-ness to something more complex, like the, like the 65 ingredient recipes of Ottolenghi

or something—I would say, yes, it can in that they're both being turned into this codified form that is itself 'the recipe'. As soon as that mode is being employed, it's recipe to me.

I've really stopped making sense, I think.

st: No, no, it makes a lot of sense. Actually, this is very close, for example, to something that I argue and still believe, I think, I argue that, you know, the way in which you are picking cherries from a tree, the way you put sugar, that's, you know, right? But even, um, even, um, um...What is her name? Uh...um... Whatever; *Chez Panisse* back in the day...

IT0506: Oh, Alice Waters? Is that her name?

AB: What?

IT0506: Waters?

AB: Brava. Alice Waters said that too.

Okay. Okay. So, I like this.

So now, onto the idea of the...the idea of the negative spaces, right? Is a, it's a way of creating identity through distinction and you can do it through practices, through... I want to see here, for you, what, um, you know, from what, even we can connect it to this report: what do you think is in that sense, um, missing? Do you see elements that are still missing? Or there should have maybe not even probably have been a report, I don't know, but suppose one wants to talk about this thing that is, in part, in effect, precisely because as we said already...that maybe you can understand in that sense why negation...is that something also? What is there that we, you know, what else to do? Is there something? I don't know. And this is... I don't even know if this is a question, or...

IT0506: The thing that's missing, for me, uh, is, is the *why*? And the *against what*? So again, with your neat use of negation, this attempt to form a database of European gastronomic legacy: Why? Who's threatening the legacy of Europe? Where...where was Europe not recorded? Why... it's not clear to me why it's needed? As soon as it becomes a matter of European gastronomic legacies, it's implying that what it's being reclaimed or recaptured out of is some muck of *not*-European gastronomic legacies.

And then my question just becomes, but why? But why? Especially in a continent that's foodstuffs have been so shaped by its historic legacy of going to everywhere else in the world and naming everywhere else in the world, defining the rest of the world, so on.

So, I guess I've been stuck for a year and a bit now on why is this needed? Who is it being made for? Who is it being made *against*? I think these are the things that really, they keep me up. These are the things that keep me up at night and make me wonder *what have I done?* Don't look at me like that or I'm going to turn the camera off [Laughs]

AB: [Laughs] No, no! It's good, it's...this also depends on, this could be...I think this is a germane question...it could also be a question for the...

Did you see anything that has been done so far in the project that tries to address that? And, um... I think this is very relevant as a question, also with respect to...so, if you think 'what is a recipe collection?' No, in this sense...Is RELISH concerned with one recipe collection or do you think...

IT0506: I don't know. I can't figure it out. I have no idea.

AB: No, I don't know. I don't think so. I'm not... I don't have any... Is it attempting to generate a recipe collection? I know that it's um...

IT0506: It's an attempt to do something that uses a vocabulary that is both trendy and completely foreign to me. It is creating a "platform". I don't know what that means. It's creating a platform for "young people". I don't know what that means. Are we making a new TikTok? Like, I don't know what that means. Uh, I don't get what any of it means, but I do think that the starting premise troubles me.

With platform, I always think of a barge. You know, in water.

AB: [Laughs]

IT0506: But I don't think we're building a barge out of recipes. So, yeah...

AB: No, no, I think this is great. This could be questions to take for the next stages, for this program, you know, the next stage is when we think about the, um, you know, other questions that should be addressed.

Um, I'd just like to explore this a little more, you know, and then we can also close, but then we want to use, I'm thinking now that the, even the, the title, right? Because There are some keywords: Legacy, European, gastronomic, these are very general. Besides, it could be, and it doesn't say that it has to be in Europe, you know, it could also be European gastronomy in Australia, in South America, right? So there is that. And there is the idea of reframing.

IT0506: Mm hm.

AB: So, from what I see, there was... in the front was the idea that, okay, we are trying to think, what could have been shared, used, rejected for future generations. We discuss questions of sustainability...you know, and maybe heritage... You know, we can focus on the fact, which, for me, for example, the way I read it, always is that we don't have the mandate to create a heritage. And we don't have the mandate to have even the boundaries of this is, this is not Europe.

But the mandate that is to think, using some boundaries, and the boundaries of European, very generic, precisely, you can guess by exclusion boundaries. What can we use these ideas for

thinking about, you know, future diets and sustainability? And how we should think about heritage? So for example, maybe we should think about heritage in the negative, or with a lot of care about what we should not try to memorialise.

IT0506: Yeah.

AB: But I mean, the point precisely...because this is a research project as opposed to like a commercial project where, yes, we want to project a certain idea of whatever, you know, so that we sell more of these products or whatever it is, you know, and none of these things, in our case, should be our goals, but it should be precisely truly to think.

IT0506: I don't think I don't think of heritage projects as inherently sinister, or bad. I don't think that they are necessarily synonymous with a kind of paligenetic vision of history. But in order for them *not* to be, there needs to be a conversation about power and historic power. And so heritage projects, that try to consolidate traditional practice and try to archive and make a repertoire of his heritage practice among, say, stateless people, or among um, indigenous nations that have become, uh, secondary citizens within their own indigenous lands—there's a very different stake there than for traditional hegemonic power to want to reconsolidate its heritage and history—and that's not being discussed anywhere in our project.

And that really troubles me a lot: that we are talking about Reimagining Heritage, Sustainability, whatnot. Well, what are we sustaining? Are we sustaining a heritage of power and are we reimagining it in a way that could be rephrased as revisionist history? Are we whitewashing it? Are we, are we like smoothing it over? This whole conversation is missing. It obviously troubles the Middle Eastern kid in the project, you know? Um, that's why I smoke so much.

AB: [laughs] No, but this is, these are, these are, I think, uh, precisely types of questions that, um, um to, to flag, for example. Because the idea was... besides, for example, to be aware of the history, the complexities of the history, or the... so in that sense, think of the Arabic part of the project. Or think of the manuscripts, that they... the ones from southern Spain from Catalonia, and it's kind of like precisely to show connections and the complexity of the boundary and not to lose that.

IT0506: Ok, if, if we have time still, you talked about the part of our project that is looking at Arab legacies within Europe, right? I think our framing there betrays a lot about our collective mindset in this project: in the period in which the Islamic Empire extended into contemporary Europe, that wasn't Europe with Arabs on top of it. We're talking about "When Europe was Islamic" but that was just not Europe. We're naturalising Europe, there is still this anachronistic tendency of, *oh, that was Europe, but it just happened to be ruled over*. It gives me the same ick as *oh, these manuscripts discussing Aristotle that were preserved and discussed and elaborated upon by Arabs for centuries, the Arab bit is unfortunate pollution, all knowledge is still European*.

And it's something that I see repeated a lot. Something that I heard a lot in the conducting of these interviews was something along the lines of, *Europe hasn't always been the hegemon, Italy*

was a colony of France and if I hear that one more time, I'm going to blow my brains out because that makes no sense: Italy was not a colony of France. Naples might have been at one point, Sicily might have been, but that wasn't Italy. That is pre-Italy. It's this taking of the present and asserting it onto the past.

I think it's important to think, to ask ourselves why, when ingredients from the big-O Orient and techniques from the big-O Orient making their way into the contemporary occident, we talk about it as that food being *introduced* to or more often *brought* to Europe. But when people are making tea in England and putting sugar in it, when Italians are cooking with tomatoes, we aren't talking about how did the Far East, the New World, how did the Caribbean, how did South Asia get *introduced* to Europe, because the European practice of going elsewhere, taking stuff and bringing it back, is being naturalised. The Italian dish with tomatoes is heritage because going to the new world is heritage, the pizza kebab is proof we need to protect heritage because *who invited the Egyptians here anyway?*

This is the basic sort of discussion of historic power that is absent for me. And now it's in record.

AB: Yeah, no, that's good. You know, we have some sort of scholarship, but it's precisely part of our role to bring some of these things into the conversation because it's an element, you know, I think, there are elements that are, besides the elements of logic, there are elements of um, of history that uh, um, in this sense, one could uh, would think that these are all to structure elements of history. But I think there should be more, regardless, because these are kinds of considerations, right?

No, I think this is good because now I'm like...thinking about history, what are the boundaries of Portugal? Or what are the boundaries of France? That's global. So, what are the boundaries in that sense, right? And what you think could be...it's, it is part of the conversation with...it's not that you can't have scholarship, it's precisely this, you know...these kinds of places we were asking about. I think they have to be part of the, uh, of the conversation, not because they are part of the initial thing friends that we talked about, which is, *okay, so you have this food used as a practice, and cooking as a practice of meaning, making, right, where the meaning that you are basic is a meaning of projecting. boundaries between populations and geographies, and engaging similarities on these recipes*, um, and, uh, like uh, not communication, sharing and identity, but, uh, they were not there before. They might do...they might be used for such purposes.

And yeah, so we have to ask ourselves this question and ask in doing this work on recipes, where do we position the construction process? Can we not take this? Probably not, I mean... I mean, but that's...that could be our next conversation,

Yeah. Yeah. I think here we have a good... this, this will make some good materials for questions for the entire project. One report that, for example, we have to write is about the European cultural institution making food culture programming. And suppose you add precisely the European Union itself sponsoring food culture programs. How do you approach that? You can't prevent this question, because you are representing and deciding, you can't say you should

refrain from doing that. But then if you engage in that, what does it mean to engage in that with understanding or self consciousness? I don't know, I don't know, like, in a politically fair way, but is there anything that can be very fully fair, or, you know, so what, what could be some guidelines that we provide?

And there are no outstanding guidelines for this, for example, so if you have to do food culture programming, we don't have the, I mean, there are scholars who write accounts about this, but what should we say to an institution? How can you evade the question? And as you know, every institution, perhaps, does some violence, and even if you are representing, you know, the most repressed and neglected community, but it's still a daily institution. Definitely, this should be one of the questions, and it's available.

Okay. Good. All right.

IT0506: I hope I answered things all right. I hope I didn't get too soapboxy.

AB: We should do a podcast here.

IT0506: You and me doing a podcast where it's always glitching? No one wants to listen to my accent; no one needs that in their headphones.

AB: Accent, I think I am the one.

IT0506: Okay. I'm going to stop recording now.

AB: Okay.

IT0506: Ciao.